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A Nation Called the Middle East: In Middle Eastern Internationalism

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Abstract

The Middle East, historically encompassing territories from Palestine to the regions near India, includes vast lands such as Lebanon and Syria, once integral to the Roman Empire. The remnants of Aladdin Keykubat's castle in Alanya and the Achaemenid ruins in Cappadocia, now in modern-day Turkey, underscore the region's deep historical significance, marked by a cohesive genetic, cultural, and historical identity. Yet, despite this unity, the Middle East remains one of the most politically fragmented and sectarian regions globally, plagued by internal conflicts and external interventions. This article examines the historical unity and subsequent political fragmentation of the Middle East, with a focus on religious sectarianism, colonialism, modern nationalism, and genetic commonalities. It also discusses the potential for fostering Internationalist ideology in the region, starting with economic, trade, and tourism cooperation.

Keywords: Internationalism, Middle East, Terrorism

Introduction

The Middle East is often described as a historically unified entity, stretching from Palestine to parts of India. The inclusion of regions like Lebanon and Syria, which were once under Roman rule, in the concept of Greater Middle East underscores the region's extensive historical and cultural continuity (Hourani, 1991). Archaeological sites such as the ruins of the Aladdin Keykubat castle in Alanya and the remains of the Achaemenid Empire in Cappadocia serve as testaments to this vast historical expanse (Curtis, 2005; Berrett, 2015).

The genetic and cultural similarities across the Middle Eastern region further reinforce this unity. Genetic studies have shown that the populations of the Middle East share significant ancestral ties, with a large proportion of genetic markers being common across diverse ethnic and national groups (Yehuda et al., 2019). For example, studies on mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) and Y-chromosome data have demonstrated a relatively homogenous genetic landscape across the Middle East, suggesting that despite historical migrations and invasions, the genetic pool has remained remarkably consistent (Cavalli-Sforza et al., 1994; Nebel et al., 2001). This genetic continuity is accompanied by the shared linguistic, religious, and cultural practices that have persisted over millennia, despite political boundaries (Lewis, 2002; Wells, 2007).

The creation of a genetic map of the Middle East reveals a complex yet interconnected web of relationships among the region's populations. This map highlights the close genetic affinities between groups traditionally seen as distinct, such as Arabs, Persians, Kurds, and Jews, suggesting a shared ancient ancestry that predates the rise of contemporary national identities (Abu-Amero et al., 2009; Behar et al., 2010). This genetic continuity, alongside the region's rich cultural and historical legacy, underscores the deep-rooted unity that has often been obscured by modern political divisions.

With an ongoing crisis in the Middle East especially in Gaza and Palestine, and discriminative and multiple standards by the international organizations (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a,b) , while the

axis of Western countries often tend to ignore or justify the violence in the Middle East by abusing the good words like “Democracy” (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024c) , there is a necessity to broaden the borders of national interests and to create outlines as well as markets for the economic growth in the region.

Such regional interest are often met by internal, external and terrorist challenges, which needs to be analyzed clearly before the empirical expansion of the idea to the real world.

Political Fragmentation and Sectarianism

Despite its historical unity, the Middle East is politically one of the most fragmented regions in the world. Sectarianism, particularly the Sunni-Shia divide, has played a significant role in exacerbating these divisions (Nasr, 2006). The political fragmentation of the Middle East can be traced back to the early Islamic period when the caliphates were divided along sectarian lines. This division was further entrenched by colonial powers, which exploited these sectarian differences to establish control over the region (Hinnebusch, 2014; Houry, 2013).

The creation of artificial borders by colonial powers in the early 20th century further fragmented the Middle East, dividing ethnic and religious communities across new national boundaries. The imposition of these borders often ignored the historical, cultural, and linguistic ties that bound the people of the region together, leading to conflicts that persist to this day (Fawcett, 2016).07:43

The Sykes-Picot Agreement of 1916 is a prime example of this, where arbitrary lines were drawn by Britain and France, setting the stage for a century of strife (Fromkin, 1989).

The Role of Modern Nationalism

Modern nationalism in the Middle East has often been at odds with the region’s historical and cultural unity. For example, Turkey’s emphasis on its Turkic (Mongolic) roots and its rejection of its Eastern Roman heritage is a case in point. This form of nationalism, which prioritizes ethnic identity over historical continuity, has

contributed to the fragmentation of the region (Keyder, 1987; Zürcher, 2004).

On the other hand, the Islamic Republic of Iran has sought to expand its influence in the Middle East through a form of Islamic internationalism, which paradoxically both unites and divides the region. The Shia-Sunni divide, which is central to Iran's political strategy, has further deepened the sectarian rift in the region, preventing the emergence of a unified Middle Eastern identity (Takeyh, 2009; Cole, 2002). Additionally, Iran's use of proxy groups in countries like Lebanon, Syria, and Iraq exemplifies how modern political strategies exploit historical sectarian divisions to further national interests (Wehrey, 2018).

The Impact of Sectarianism on Identity

The sectarian divisions within Islam have not only shaped the political landscape of the Middle East but have also had a profound impact on the region's identity. The existence of multiple caliphs and the theological differences between Sunni and Shia Islam have created a fragmented political and social system within a region that shares a common religious philosophy (Ayubi, 1995; Esposito, 2005). This fragmentation is reflected in the works of Islamic mystics like Rumi, who, despite advocating for unity and spiritual transcendence, acknowledged the inherent divisions within the religious and political systems of his time (Schimmel, 1993).

Rumi's famous line, "Die before you die; you are all kings and princes," illustrates the tension between the ideal of spiritual unity and the reality of political division. His gnostic approach, which emphasized the ultimate futility of worldly power and the transient nature of political systems, can be seen as both a critique of and a response to the fragmented nature of the Middle Eastern polity (Lewis, 2000).

Historical Context and Genetic Continuity

The Middle East is often described as a historically unified entity, stretching from Palestine to parts of India. The inclusion of regions like Lebanon and Syria, which were once under Roman rule, in the concept of Greater Middle East underscores the region's extensive historical and cultural continuity (Hourani, 1991). Archaeological

sites such as the ruins of the Aladdin Keykubat castle in Alanya and the remains of the Achaemenid Empire in Cappadocia serve as testaments to this vast historical expanse (Curtis, 2005; Berrett, 2015).

Historical Maps of Ancient Empires and Middle Eastern Borders

The definition of the Middle East's borders has always been fluid, shaped by the rise and fall of ancient empires that dominated the region. Historical maps of empires such as the Sumerians, Achaemenids, Parthians, and Sasanians provide crucial insights into the geographical scope and political influence that have historically defined the region.

The Sumerian civilization (c. 4500–1900 BCE), considered one of the earliest known civilizations, was centered in the southern part of Mesopotamia (modern-day Iraq) and extended its influence over parts of the Levant and Persia. The Sumerians established city-states such as Ur and Uruk, laying the groundwork for subsequent empires in the region (Kramer, 1963).

The Achaemenid Empire (c. 550–330 BCE), founded by Cyrus the Great, represents one of the largest empires in history, stretching from the Balkans and Eastern Europe in the west to the Indus Valley in the east. The Achaemenid Empire's borders encompassed much of the modern Middle East, including Iran, Iraq, the Levant, Anatolia, and Egypt. This vast expanse helped unify diverse cultures under a centralized administration and contributed to the region's shared cultural and genetic heritage (Briant, 2002; Cook, 1983).

Following the Achaemenids, the Parthian Empire (c. 247 BCE–224 CE) controlled a vast territory stretching from the Euphrates River to eastern Iran. The Parthians were known for their semi-nomadic nature and their ability to maintain control over a large, culturally diverse region despite frequent conflicts with the Roman Empire. The Parthian Empire played a critical role in maintaining the continuity of Persian culture and governance in the Middle East (Daryaee, 2012).

The Sasanian Empire (c. 224–651 CE), which succeeded the Parthians, marked the last great Iranian empire before the rise of Islam. At its height, the Sasanian Empire controlled all of modern-

day Iran, Iraq, parts of the Caucasus, the Levant, and Central Asia. The Sasanian period is particularly significant for its influence on the cultural and religious landscape of the Middle East, as it was a time of significant Zoroastrian religious development and administrative sophistication (Frye, 1984; Shahbazi, 2002).

These empires' borders, as illustrated in historical maps, highlight the Middle East's role as a crossroads of civilizations, where various cultures, languages, and religions intermingled. The geographic span of these empires also underscores the historical continuity of the Middle East as a unified region, despite the modern political borders that now divide it.

The overlapping territories of these ancient empires reflect a shared historical and cultural space that transcends contemporary national boundaries. This historical perspective challenges the modern conception of the Middle East as a collection of fragmented nation-states, instead highlighting its legacy as a region defined by expansive, integrative empires (Curtis, 2005; Potts, 2012).

By studying these historical maps, scholars can better understand the long-standing connections among the peoples of the Middle East and how these connections have shaped the region's identity over millennia. The enduring legacy of these empires is still evident today, in the region's shared cultural practices, languages, and, as genetic studies show, its remarkably cohesive population (Cavalli-Sforza et al., 1994; Wells, 2007).

Sectarian and Ideological Fragmentation of the Middle East After Islam

Figure 1 A map illustrating the rise and expansion of early Islamic caliphates from the Prophet Muhammad until the 9th century.

The advent of Islam in the 7th century (Fig. 1) profoundly transformed the Middle East, unifying vast territories under a single religious and political framework. However, the initial unity established under the Rashidun and subsequent Umayyad and Abbasid Caliphates gradually gave way to significant sectarian and ideological fragmentation, laying the groundwork for the divisions that continue to define the region today.

The Sunni-Shia Divide

One of the most consequential rifts in the Islamic world emerged shortly after the death of Prophet Muhammad in 632 CE, centering on the question of rightful leadership of the Muslim community. This dispute led to the formation of two major sects: Sunnis, who

supported the election of caliphs from among the Prophet's companions, and Shias, who believed that leadership should remain within the Prophet's family, specifically with his cousin and son-in-law, Ali (Halm, 1997).

The Sunni-Shia divide became not just a religious difference but a deeply ingrained political and social fault line that has shaped the power dynamics in the Middle East for centuries. The early Islamic period saw the establishment of Shia dynasties, such as the Fatimids in North Africa and the Safavids in Persia, which often found themselves in opposition to the Sunni-dominated Caliphates of the Umayyads and Abbasids (Hodgson, 1974; Marshall, 2017). These sectarian divides were further compounded by theological differences, particularly in the interpretation of Islamic law and the role of religious authority.

The Safavid Empire's (1501–1736) adoption of Twelver Shia Islam as the state religion was a significant turning point in the sectarian landscape of the Middle East. This move not only solidified the Shia identity within Persia (modern-day Iran) but also set the stage for enduring rivalry with the Sunni Ottoman Empire, which dominated much of the rest of the region (Ruthven, 2012). This sectarian rivalry often manifested in military conflicts and political alliances that sought to leverage religious differences to gain strategic advantages (Matthee, 1999).

Ideological Fragmentation

In addition to sectarian divisions, the Middle East has also experienced significant ideological fragmentation, particularly in the post-colonial era. The rise of various nationalist, socialist, and Islamist ideologies throughout the 20th century further fragmented the region's political landscape.

Arab nationalism, which emerged in the early 20th century as a response to Ottoman rule and Western colonialism, sought to unite Arab-speaking populations under a common identity. However, this movement was often at odds with the realities of political power, leading to tensions between different Arab states, as well as between Arab nationalists and other ethnic and religious groups within the

Middle East (Dawisha, 2005). The failure of Arab nationalist projects, such as the United Arab Republic (a political union between Egypt and Syria from 1958 to 1961), exemplifies the challenges of creating a unified ideological front in a region marked by deep-seated divisions (Hinnebusch, 2003).

The rise of political Islam in the latter half of the 20th century introduced another layer of ideological complexity. Movements such as the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt and the Iranian Revolution of 1979 reflected a turn towards Islamism as a political ideology, seeking to establish governance based on Islamic principles. These movements often clashed with both secular nationalist regimes and each other, further deepening ideological divisions in the region (Esposito, 1997; Roy, 1994).

In the aftermath of the Iranian Revolution, the Middle East saw a significant increase in sectarian tensions, particularly between Sunni and Shia communities. Iran's attempt to export its revolutionary ideology to other parts of the Middle East exacerbated sectarian conflicts in countries like Iraq, Lebanon, and Bahrain.07:48

The Iran-Iraq War (1980–1988), in particular, was fueled by sectarian rhetoric, with Saddam Hussein's Sunni-dominated regime framing the conflict as a defense against Shia expansionism (Takeyh, 2009).

The ideological landscape of the Middle East today is a complex tapestry of competing visions for the region's future. From secular Arab nationalism to Sunni and Shia Islamism, and from theocratic governance models to secular liberalism, the Middle East is characterized by a multiplicity of ideologies that often conflict with one another. These ideological divisions are not just confined to state actors but are also reflected in the region's many non-state actors, including militias, political movements, and terrorist organizations, each promoting their own vision for the region (Gerges, 2016).

The Challenges of Middle Eastern Internationalism

The concept of Middle Eastern internationalism, or a unified regional identity, poses a significant challenge to the traditional

power structures of Arab sheikhs, caliphs, and monarchs. These rulers, deeply invested in maintaining their internal sovereignty, view the strict control of borders as essential to preserving their authority. This perspective is echoed in the Quran, where the Bedouin Arabs are described as being "more hard in disbelief and hypocrisy" (Quran 9:97), indicating a resistance to broader unification and the potential loss of local power (Ibn Kathir, 2003).

This ideology of fragmentation has other formidable adversaries, notably terrorism, which exploits these divisions to further destabilize the region. The Islamic Republic of Iran has attempted to counteract this fragmentation by establishing what is often referred to as the "Shia Crescent," a sphere of influence stretching from Iran through Iraq and Syria to Lebanon. This strategic move is seen as an effort to overcome Arab disunity, though it simultaneously exacerbates sectarian tensions within the region (Nasr, 2007).

While both Shia and Sunni branches of Islam inherently possess sectarian and separatist tendencies, the issue of Palestine reveals the depth of division among Arab nations and other Middle Eastern peoples. Despite the shared plight of Palestinian occupation and the collective suffering under external aggression, internal divisions, such as those between Hamas, Islamic Jihad, and Fatah, prevent the formation of a unified policy or approach (Hroub, 2006).

Further complicating the regional landscape are the Kurdish celebrations amidst the broader context of genocide, where Kurdish leaders seek alignment with Israel as a path to independence from Middle Eastern ties. This situation reflects both public ignorance and the influence of external powers in shaping the collective consciousness of Middle Eastern nations. Many in the region fail to recognize what might be lost in this process of alignment with global capitalism, a trend that threatens to erode regional identities and autonomy (Gunter, 2008).

Even within Palestine, a land marked by the shared experience of occupation and violence, sectarian conflicts and political factionalism, such as those among Hamas, Islamic Jihad, and Fatah, hinder the development of a cohesive strategy for resistance and governance (Hroub, 2006). The ongoing disunity underscores the broader challenges facing Middle Eastern internationalism, where

internal divisions continue to thwart efforts toward regional solidarity.

Ultimately, the vision of Middle Eastern internationalism remains tied to a messianic hope, symbolized by the awaited return of the Mahdi or the Messiah, who is expected to heal the hearts of the people and bring their thoughts closer together. This millennia-old Arab aspiration reflects a deep-seated desire for unity and peace, a vision that remains elusive in the face of the region's enduring divisions (Khatab, 2007).

Conclusion

The Middle East, despite its historical and cultural unity, remains one of the most politically fragmented regions in the world. The region's genetic and cultural continuity, evident in its shared linguistic and religious practices, stands in stark contrast to the political divisions that have been exacerbated by sectarianism, colonialism, and modern nationalism.

The Sunni-Shia divide, rooted in early Islamic history, remains one of the most enduring sources of conflict in the region. Meanwhile, the proliferation of competing ideological movements in the 20th and 21st centuries has further fragmented the Middle East, making the dream of regional unity increasingly elusive. Understanding these deep-seated divisions is crucial for any attempt to navigate or resolve the ongoing conflicts in the Middle East.

With an ongoing crisis in Gaza and ignorance by the western and international media, there is an increasing need to pursue a uniting action for a harmonious growth and competitive economy in the Middle Eastern countries based on the ease of trade, tourism and economic factors. Such an Ideal despite having practical challenges, stands as a hope for the decades to come.

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The Dynamics of Conflict in the Middle East: Actors, Instruments of Tension, and the Role of Sectarian Violence and the Israel-Palestinian War

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Abstract

The Middle East remains one of the most volatile regions in the world, with conflicts deeply rooted in historical, religious, and geopolitical factors. This article explores the key actors who benefit from and perpetuate these tensions, including Israel, extremist Islamic groups, arms dealers, and avengers of violence. It also analyzes the tools of tension creation, such as news engineering, the instrumentalization of religion and history, and geopolitical factors like water scarcity and migration. Special emphasis is placed on the roles of sectarian violence and the Israel-Palestinian conflict, which have both fueled and been exacerbated by the region's broader dynamics. By examining these elements, the article provides a comprehensive understanding of the ongoing conflicts and potential paths to peace.

The hope for a violence free Middle-East with expansion of economic, tourism and trade borders remains elusive without finding proper solutions to the overwhelming tensions in the region.

Keywords: Middle East, Internationalism, Gaza Crisis

Introduction

The Middle East has long been a focal point of conflict, driven by a complex interplay of historical grievances, religious tensions, and strategic interests. Among the most significant factors contributing to the region's instability are sectarian violence and the enduring Israel-Palestinian conflict. These issues not only act as immediate triggers for violence but also serve as catalysts for broader regional instability. In previous works, the potential for unifying Middle Eastern values has been explored as a necessary response to the disparate standards imposed on Middle Eastern identity (Davoudpour, 2024a). Additionally, the misuse of terms such as "Democracy" and "Terrorism" to manipulate perceptions and policies concerning the Middle East has been critically examined (Davoudpour, 2024c). These studies have underscored the importance of addressing religious sectarianism, colonial legacies, modern nationalism, and the region's genetic commonalities to foster a more cohesive and peaceful Middle East.

This article builds on these insights by emphasizing the need to understand the motivations and methods of key actors in the region, as well as the historical and religious narratives they exploit. Such understanding is crucial for developing effective strategies to mitigate conflict and promote peace. The foundations of contemporary Middle Eastern society are deeply rooted in the Islamic empires and the reign of the Islamic Caliphates up until the 7th and 8th centuries A.D., alongside the teachings of Prophet Muhammad (Davoudpour, 2024d). While a comprehensive overhaul of Islamic teachings is neither feasible nor necessary, fostering respect for these teachings through societal reforms, along with promoting economic, trade, and tourism cooperation, offers a potential pathway toward stability (Davoudpour, 2024e). This article will explore these themes, with a particular focus on the roles of sectarian violence and the Israel-Palestinian conflict in shaping the region's current dynamics.

Classification of Actors Perpetuating Tension

1. **Israel and Its Strategic Interests** Israel's role in the Middle East is pivotal, especially in the context of its conflict with the Palestinians. The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is one of the most enduring and

polarizing issues in the region, shaping not only Israeli and Palestinian lives but also influencing the broader Middle Eastern geopolitics. Israel's approach to security, which includes targeted assassinations of Palestinian leaders and military operations in the Gaza Strip, has often been criticized for exacerbating tensions and undermining peace efforts (Lynfield, 2020). Furthermore, Israel's settlement expansion in the West Bank has been a major point of contention, leading to accusations that it is not genuinely interested in a two-state solution (United Nations, 2022). Israel's strategic goal of maintaining its security and regional dominance often clashes with Palestinian aspirations for statehood, creating a cycle of violence and retaliation. In the course of ongoing Gaza crisis in July-2024, the assassination of Ismail Haniye the chief peace negotiator of Hamas in Tehran¹ revealed that the global attempts to reach a peace agreement is often deliberately breached by the Israeli government.

2. **Extremist Islamic Groups** Extremist Islamic groups such as Hamas, Hezbollah, ISIS, and Al-Qaeda have significantly contributed to the sectarian violence in the Middle East. These groups often exploit religious and sectarian identities to mobilize support and justify their actions (Byman, 2021). Hamas, for instance, emerged as a major force in Palestinian politics in the late 1980s, advocating for armed resistance against Israel. Its charter explicitly calls for the destruction of Israel, and its violent confrontations with Israeli forces have led to multiple wars, most notably the Gaza Wars of 2008-09, 2012, 2014, and 2021 (Jones & Milton-Edwards, 2021) and the most important war of 2024 with more than 186,000 direct and indirect casualties (Khatib et al., 2024), leading to destruction the infrastructure of Gaza and activation of the convention of Genocide in the International Court of Justice² and provisional and advisory measures against Israel and some of its

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ismail_Haniyeh

² International Court of Justice. (2024, January 26). *Order of 26 January 2024* (Document No. 192-20240126-ORD-01-00-EN). Case No. 192 - Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide in the Gaza Strip (South Africa v. Israel), Incidental Proceedings: Provisional measures. <https://www.icij-cij.org/en/case/192/orders>

allies³⁴ again. Hezbollah, another key player, operates with the backing of Iran and has been involved in conflicts across Lebanon and Syria, further intensifying Sunni-Shia tensions in the region (Saab, 2021). These groups' activities contribute to a broader pattern of sectarian violence, particularly between Sunni and Shia Muslims, which destabilizes the region and perpetuates cycles of revenge and retaliation.

3. **Arms Dealers and the Death Merchants** The global arms trade is a critical factor in sustaining conflicts in the Middle East, particularly those driven by sectarian and nationalist motivations. Major arms producers, such as the United States, Russia, and European countries, supply weapons to various factions in the region, fueling the cycle of violence (SIPRI, 2023). For instance, during the Syrian Civil War, multiple external actors provided arms to different factions, with the U.S. and Russia backing opposing sides, thus prolonging the conflict and deepening sectarian divisions (Weiss, 2022). The proliferation of arms in the region has not only escalated conflicts but also empowered non-state actors like Hezbollah and Hamas, who use these weapons to challenge state authorities and intensify sectarian violence.
4. **Avengers of Lost Ones** The cycle of revenge is a powerful driver of violence in the Middle East, particularly in the context of sectarian conflicts and the Israel-Palestinian war. Groups and individuals who have suffered losses in these conflicts often seek retribution, leading to further violence (Khashan, 2020). In the Israel-Palestinian context, the desire for revenge has fueled acts of terrorism, military reprisals, and civilian casualties on both sides. This cycle of violence is perpetuated by deeply ingrained narratives of victimization and martyrdom, which are often exploited by political and religious leaders to mobilize support and justify continued hostilities (Jones & Milton-Edwards, 2021). The impact of these narratives is particularly evident in the ongoing clashes

³ International Court of Justice. (2024, July 19). *Alleged breaches of certain international obligations in respect of the Occupied Palestinian Territory (Nicaragua v. Germany)*, Order. General List No. 193. <https://www.icj-cij.org/en/case/193/orders>

⁴ International Court of Justice. (2024, July 19). *Legal consequences arising from the policies and practices of Israel in the Occupied Palestinian Territory, including East Jerusalem*, Order. General List No. 186. <https://www.icj-cij.org/en/case/186/orders>

between Israelis and Palestinians, where each new round of violence begets another, leaving little room for reconciliation.

The Role of Sectarian Violence in the Middle East

Sectarian violence, particularly between Sunni and Shia Muslims, is one of the most persistent and destructive forces in the Middle East. This divide is rooted in historical, theological, and political differences dating back to the early years of Islam. The conflict over who should lead the Muslim community after the Prophet Muhammad's death led to the formation of two main branches of Islam: Sunni, which represents the majority, and Shia, which is dominant in countries like Iran and Iraq (Nasr, 2022).

1. **Sunni-Shia Conflict** The Sunni-Shia divide has been a major source of tension in the region, exacerbated by the geopolitical ambitions of regional powers like Saudi Arabia and Iran. These two nations, representing the Sunni and Shia blocs respectively, have engaged in a proxy war across the Middle East, supporting opposing factions in conflicts in Syria, Yemen, Iraq, and Lebanon (Valbjørn, 2022). In Syria, for example, the Assad regime, backed by Shia-majority Iran and Hezbollah, has fought against a predominantly Sunni opposition supported by Saudi Arabia and other Gulf states. This conflict has not only devastated Syria but also deepened sectarian animosities across the region, with far-reaching consequences for regional stability (Weiss, 2022).
2. **The Role of External Powers** External powers have often exacerbated sectarian conflicts in the Middle East by aligning with one side or the other for strategic reasons. The United States, for instance, has historically supported Sunni-majority countries like Saudi Arabia and the Gulf states, while Russia has aligned itself with Shia-majority Iran and the Assad regime in Syria (Gause, 2019). These alliances have turned local sectarian conflicts into broader geopolitical struggles, with devastating consequences for civilian populations. The involvement of external powers has also made it more difficult to resolve these conflicts, as any potential settlement must account for the interests of both local and international actors.
3. **Impact on Regional Stability** Sectarian violence has a profound impact on the stability of the Middle East. It not only leads to widespread death and displacement but also undermines the social

fabric of the region, making it difficult for communities to coexist peacefully (Lewis, 2021). The Sunni-Shia divide has also contributed to the rise of extremist groups like ISIS, which exploited sectarian tensions to gain support and territory in Iraq and Syria. The collapse of state authority in these countries has created a power vacuum that has been filled by militias and other non-state actors, further complicating efforts to restore peace and stability (Byman, 2021).

The Israel-Palestinian Conflict: A Catalyst for Regional Instability

The Israel-Palestinian conflict is a central issue in Middle Eastern politics and a major source of tension both within and outside the region. The conflict, which began in the early 20th century with the rise of Zionism and Arab nationalism, has evolved into a complex struggle over land, identity, and sovereignty.

1. **Historical Context** The roots of the Israel-Palestinian conflict lie in the competing national aspirations of Jews and Arabs in the early 20th century. The Balfour Declaration of 1917, in which the British government expressed support for the establishment of a "national home for the Jewish people" in Palestine, was a turning point in the conflict. The declaration was seen by Arab leaders as a betrayal, leading to decades of violence and unrest (Morris, 2021). The creation of the state of Israel in 1948 and the subsequent wars in 1948, 1967, and 1973 further deepened the conflict, resulting in the displacement of hundreds of thousands of Palestinians and the occupation of Palestinian territories by Israel (Khalidi, 2020).
2. **The Role of Religion** Religion plays a significant role in the Israel-Palestinian conflict, particularly in the context of Jerusalem, a city sacred to Jews, Muslims, and Christians alike. The status of Jerusalem, which Israel considers its undivided capital and Palestinians claim as the capital of a future Palestinian state, is one of the most contentious issues in the conflict. Religious narratives are often used by both sides to justify their claims to the land and their actions in the conflict. For example, Jewish settlers in the West Bank often cite biblical promises as the basis for their right to the land, while Palestinian leaders invoke Islamic teachings to rally support for their cause (Friedland & Hecht, 2021).

3. **Impact on Regional and Global Politics** The Israel-Palestinian conflict has far-reaching implications for regional and global politics. It has been a major factor in the rise of anti-Israel sentiment across the Arab world, fueling extremist movements and contributing to the radicalization of populations (Gerges, 2021). The conflict has also strained relations between Israel and its neighbors, particularly Lebanon, Syria, and Jordan, leading to periodic outbreaks of violence and instability. On a global level, the conflict has polarized international opinion, with the United States and most Western countries supporting Israel, while much of the developing world, including many Muslim-majority countries, supports the Palestinian cause (Smith, 2021).
4. **Attempts at Peace** Despite numerous attempts at peace, including the Oslo Accords of the 1990s and the Camp David Summit in 2000, the Israel-Palestinian conflict remains unresolved. The failure of these peace efforts can be attributed to a range of factors, including mutual distrust, the influence of extremist groups, and the lack of political will on both sides (Ross, 2020). The continued expansion of Israeli settlements in the West Bank and the blockade of Gaza have further complicated the situation, making it difficult to achieve a two-state solution, which is widely considered the most viable path to peace (Lustick, 2021).

Analysis and Discussion

The Middle East's conflicts, particularly those driven by sectarian violence and the Israel-Palestinian war, are deeply entrenched, with multiple actors and factors contributing to the region's instability. The Sunni-Shia divide has been a major source of tension, exacerbated by the geopolitical ambitions of regional powers like Saudi Arabia and Iran. The involvement of external powers has turned local sectarian conflicts into broader geopolitical struggles, with devastating consequences for the region's stability.

The Israel-Palestinian conflict, with its roots in historical grievances and religious narratives, continues to be a central issue in Middle Eastern politics. The failure to resolve this conflict has not only perpetuated violence between Israelis and Palestinians but has also contributed to broader regional instability. The conflict has fueled anti-Israel sentiment across the Arab world, radicalized populations, and strained relations between Israel and its neighbors.

The tools used to perpetuate these conflicts, such as news engineering and the instrumentalization of religion and history, ensure that the region remains mired in violence. The manipulation of narratives and the exploitation of religious and historical grievances make it difficult to achieve peace and reconciliation. The influx of arms into the region further complicates efforts to resolve these conflicts, as it empowers non-state actors and perpetuates cycles of violence.

Conclusion

The ongoing conflicts in the Middle East, particularly those driven by sectarian violence and the Israel-Palestinian war, are the result of a complex interplay of state and non-state actors, each with its own motivations and objectives. The tools used to perpetuate these conflicts, from misinformation and propaganda to the exploitation of religious and historical narratives, ensure that the region remains unstable and prone to violence. To address these challenges, the international community must adopt a multifaceted approach that considers the diverse interests and tactics at play. This includes promoting dialogue and understanding among the region's various factions, addressing the root causes of conflict, and reducing the flow of arms into the region. Only by tackling these issues head-on can there be any hope for lasting peace in the Middle East.

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Contemporary Superhuman Ideals: From Nietzsche and Harari to Bollywood and Gandhi

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Abstract

The concept of the "superhuman" has evolved through philosophical, literary, and popular culture lenses, finding its most dramatic representations in the works of Friedrich Nietzsche and contemporary thinker Yuval Noah Harari. This paper explores the juxtaposition of Nietzsche's Übermensch and Harari's god-like future humans against the backdrop of cinematic heroes in Bollywood and Hollywood and the non-violent, moral figure of Mahatma Gandhi. The article delves into how these varied representations of superhumanity reflect different cultural and ethical values, particularly in the context of contemporary Indian politics and global conflicts such as the Israeli-Palestinian situation.

Keywords: Gandhi, Übermensch, Harari, Nietzsche, Homo Deus

Introduction

The concept of the superhuman, as envisioned by Nietzsche and later by Yuval Noah Harari, represents a being that transcends ordinary human limitations, either through sheer willpower or technological advancement. Nietzsche's Übermensch embodies a philosophical ideal of self-overcoming and moral revaluation, striving to create new values that go beyond conventional morality. In contrast, Harari's vision of future humans, enhanced by technology, suggests a literal transcendence of human limitations, where scientific and technological advancements enable a new form of god-like existence (Nietzsche, 1883; Harari, 2015).

This paper explores how these philosophical ideas contrast with the exaggerated depictions of heroism in Bollywood and Hollywood, as well as the moral fortitude exemplified by Mahatma Gandhi. These differing conceptions of superhumanity expose deep cultural and ethical divides, particularly when applied to contemporary issues like India's political stance and the Israeli-Palestinian conflict.

Unlike Harari's vision, which emphasizes the role of science, real-world conflicts such as those in Gaza reveal a stark separation between scientific merit, wisdom, intellect, and moral considerations (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a,b). In these conflicts, a war between technological prowess and moral principles unfolds, where an excessive military budget is deployed against a relatively less developed but religiously motivated nation (Davoudpour, A.R., 2004c). This situation underscores the tension between scientific advancement and ethical responsibility, raising questions about whether technological superiority truly equates to moral progress or the application of wisdom. This also prompts inquiries into the authenticity of science when divorced from capitalistic means, i.e., money (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024d,e).

Real human conflicts present a contest between philosophical viewpoints and challenges to the evolution of human perspectives (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024f,g). These challenges are crucial for humanity to reassess its observational and empirical approaches to the future, though, unfortunately, not everyone succeeds in passing these critical tests.

Nietzsche's Übermensch and Harari's God-like Humans

Friedrich Nietzsche introduced the concept of the Übermensch (Overman or Superman) in his work *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*. Nietzsche's Übermensch is not bound by conventional morality; instead, he creates his own values and rises above the mediocrity of the masses. This superhuman is characterized by a will to power, the ability to impose his will on the world, and the courage to embrace life's challenges without the comfort of traditional religious or moral frameworks (Nietzsche, 1883).

Yuval Noah Harari, on the other hand, envisions a future where humans, through advancements in technology and biology, could become god-like beings. Harari's "Homo Deus" represents a new kind of superhuman, one that surpasses biological limitations through artificial intelligence, genetic engineering, and other forms of enhancement (Harari, 2015). Unlike Nietzsche's philosophical ideal, Harari's vision is rooted in the potential for scientific and technological evolution to redefine what it means to be human.

Bollywood's Cinematic Heroes: A Cultural Interpretation of Superhumanity

Bollywood's portrayal of heroes can be seen as a cultural interpretation of the superhuman ideal. These heroes, who can catch arrows with their teeth and perform impossible feats, reflect a desire for larger-than-life figures who can overcome any obstacle. However, this representation is more fantasy than philosophical ideal, focusing on physical invincibility rather than moral or intellectual superiority. These characters are adored by audiences for their ability to defy the laws of nature, symbolizing a wish-fulfillment that aligns more with Nietzsche's idea of transcending the ordinary, albeit in a more literal and less profound manner.

In contrast to both Nietzsche's and Harari's superhumans, Bollywood heroes embody a superficial form of greatness that is rooted in physical strength and cinematic spectacle. They are symbols of resilience and power but lack the deeper philosophical or ethical dimensions that characterize Nietzsche's Übermensch or Harari's technologically enhanced future beings.

Hollywood's Interpretation of Superhumanity: A Comparative Analysis

Hollywood, like Bollywood, has its own tradition of depicting superhuman figures, often through the lens of superheroes in blockbuster films. Characters such as Superman, Batman, and the Avengers epitomize the Western cultural interpretation of the superhuman. These figures, much like their Bollywood counterparts, are portrayed with extraordinary abilities that allow them to combat evil and protect humanity. However, Hollywood's approach to the superhuman often incorporates a deeper exploration of moral dilemmas, identity crises, and the responsibilities that come with great power (Burke, 2015).

Unlike Bollywood's often straightforward portrayal of physical invincibility, Hollywood's superheroes are frequently depicted as struggling with the ethical implications of their powers. For example, in *Man of Steel* (2013), Superman wrestles with the moral responsibility of using his powers for the greater good, reflecting a tension between Nietzschean self-assertion and a more altruistic, self-sacrificial ideal (McGowan, 2013). This mirrors Harari's discussions on the ethical challenges posed by future technologies, where the enhancement of human capabilities could lead to new forms of inequality and moral conflict (Harari, 2015).

Moreover, Hollywood films often delve into the consequences of unchecked power, as seen in *The Dark Knight* (2008), where Batman confronts the chaos unleashed by his vigilante justice. This reflects a cautionary stance on the Nietzschean *Übermensch*, suggesting that the pursuit of power without moral consideration can lead to devastating outcomes (Jest, 2008).

In comparison to Gandhi's moral superhumanity, Hollywood's heroes often find themselves navigating a complex landscape of ethical choices, where the line between heroism and tyranny can become blurred. This nuanced portrayal adds a layer of depth to the superhuman ideal, highlighting the potential dangers of power divorced from ethical grounding. Gandhi's approach, rooted in non-violence and ethical consistency, contrasts sharply with Hollywood's depiction of the superhuman, suggesting that true heroism may require not just extraordinary abilities but also a steadfast commitment to moral principles (Nanda, 1989).

This comparative analysis of Hollywood, Bollywood, and Gandhi's legacy underscores the diverse ways in which cultures interpret the idea of the superhuman. While Hollywood and Bollywood celebrate physical prowess and the ability to overcome insurmountable odds, Gandhi's life and philosophy remind us that the greatest superhuman qualities might be found in humility, compassion, and unwavering ethical commitment.

Gandhi's Non-Violence: A Different Kind of Superhuman

Mahatma Gandhi's as a living model for superhuman achievements during his lifetime had a different approach to life which presents a stark contrast to the superhuman ideals of Nietzsche and Harari. Gandhi, with his frail physique and commitment to non-violence, represents a form of moral superhumanity that is grounded in ethical principles rather than physical or technological superiority. His leadership in India's independence movement was marked by his unwavering belief in Ahimsa (non-violence) and Satyagraha (truth-force), concepts that emphasize moral courage over brute strength (Nanda, 1989).

Gandhi's correspondence with Adolf Hitler, in which he urged the dictator to embrace non-violence, is a powerful example of his belief in the superiority of moral force over physical power (Gandhi, 1939). In this sense, Gandhi's superhumanity is defined not by his ability to dominate others, as in Nietzsche's *Übermensch*, nor by transcending human limitations through technology, as in Harari's *Homo Deus*, but by his capacity for compassion, humility, and ethical consistency.

Contemporary Indian Politics and the Legacy of Superhuman Ideals

The contrast between these different superhuman ideals becomes particularly relevant in the context of contemporary Indian politics. Certain factions in India have supported violent state actions, such as those by Israel in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, which seems to align more with a Nietzschean will to power than with Gandhi's principles of non-violence (Varshney, 2021). This support reflects a departure from Gandhi's legacy and a move towards a more aggressive, power-centric worldview.

Moreover, the notion of the superhuman in Bollywood, which is rooted in fantasy, contrasts sharply with the real-world implications of supporting state violence. While cinematic heroes emerge unscathed from battles, real-life conflicts result in significant human suffering, particularly for vulnerable populations like children in Palestine (Said, 1979). This dichotomy highlights the ethical challenges of reconciling the ideal of the superhuman with the realities of political and military power.

Conclusion

The exploration of superhuman ideals from Nietzsche to Harari, and their manifestation in Cinema and Gandhi's life, reveals a spectrum of interpretations that reflect different cultural, philosophical, and ethical values. Nietzsche's Übermensch and Harari's god-like humans represent different forms of transcendence—philosophical and technological—while Cinematic heroes offer a more superficial, though culturally significant, interpretation. Gandhi's approach, however, stands as a reminder that true greatness may lie not in the transcendence of physical limitations but in the moral courage to uphold justice and non-violence. As contemporary global conflicts present continues to grapple with these conflicting ideals, the need to revisit and re-evaluate the true nature of heroism and superhumanity becomes increasingly important.

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Samsara, a Thousand Cycles of False and Truth

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Abstract

In the quest for truth, it is often the case that a seeker, perhaps an accomplished philosopher or a martyr endowed with the highest merits and virtues, dedicates their entire being to uncovering that essence—an elixir of life, a fountain of youth. This pursuit is not merely a search for knowledge, but a deep, consuming journey towards understanding the very nature of existence.

Contrasting this, a being who is not driven by such a search may find a certain peace in accepting life as it is, unchallenged by the deeper questions that beckon the seeker. However, the wayfarer—one who treads the path with purpose—encounters something along their journey. The truths they uncover, though profound and illuminating at each step, inevitably become obsolete as they advance. Yet, this obsolescence does not negate their truth; rather, it signifies the transient nature of understanding as the seeker evolves.

Similarly, the non-seeker may stumble upon something—a falsehood—that also loses its hold over time. This falsehood, like the truths discovered by the wayfarer, is subject to the same impermanence.

This dynamic journey resembles the lotus of the path, a symbol with thousands of petals, each representing a layer of truth. The lotus, with its infinite layers, mirrors the infinity of creation itself. Yet, the creator—the source from which all truth and falsehood emanate—remains beyond comprehension, beyond size, beyond knowledge. The creator transcends all, while the creation,

with its infinite possibilities, unfolds like the ever-blooming lotus, offering glimpses of truth at every turn.

Keywords: Samsara, Wisdom, Imhal, Istidraj

Introduction

The pursuit of truth has been a central theme in both philosophical and mystical traditions, often depicted as a quest for the essence of life, an elixir that promises eternal youth and understanding (Davoudpour, Zandi, & Mikaeil, 2024). This quest is not merely an intellectual exercise but a profound journey that engages the entire being of the seeker. Such seekers are often portrayed as philosophers or martyrs who, driven by a deep sense of purpose, invest all their capacities in the search for truth. Their journey is characterized by a relentless pursuit of the essence of existence, a quest that transcends mere knowledge acquisition and touches the very core of what it means to be human. In this context we discuss the eternal but transient nature of the Truth, where a new fact is derived from the previous knowledge which is called the higher truth in Avesta¹ and Zoroastrian Prayer “Ašem . vohu “¹ the most recited prayer of the religion, the higher truth is the fruit of pursuit of truth.

“Righteousness is best (of all that is) good.

As desired, what is being desired

is truth for him who (represents) best truth.”

In Islamic teaching, “Istidraj”² and “Imhal” are designated steps for the people or entities who pursue falsehood and consequently fall into greater falsehoods.

¹ Ašem . vohu . vahištem . asti... Uštā . asti...Uštā . ahmāi . hyat . ašāi . vahištāi . ašem

² Istidraj means gradually and Imhal means given time and granting respite

Samsara in Buddhism

In Buddhism, *samsara* refers to the cyclical nature of existence, a continuous cycle of birth, death, and rebirth. This endless wheel of life, driven by karma and delusion, traps beings in a perpetual state of suffering, known as *dukkha* (Gethin, 1998). Samsara is often depicted as a vast ocean, where beings are adrift, caught in the currents of their desires, attachments, and ignorance. Each life within samsara is influenced by past actions and the cravings that keep beings tethered to the cycle (Harvey, 2013).

The fundamental problem of samsara lies in its inherent dissatisfaction. No matter the circumstances, whether one is born into pleasure or pain, wealth or poverty, the conditions of samsaric existence are impermanent and thus incapable of providing lasting fulfillment. This impermanence, or *anicca*, ensures that every pleasure eventually fades, every achievement loses its luster, and every life ends in death, only to begin anew (Rahula, 1974).

Buddhism teaches that the way to break free from samsara is through the attainment of enlightenment, or *nirvana*. Nirvana represents the cessation of the cycle, the end of suffering, and the realization of the ultimate truth (Keown, 2000). It is a state where the flames of desire and ignorance are extinguished, allowing the mind to rest in perfect peace and wisdom. The path to nirvana involves ethical conduct, meditation, and the development of wisdom, particularly the understanding of the Four Noble Truths and the Eightfold Path (Conze, 1993).

In this way, samsara and nirvana represent the fundamental dichotomy in Buddhist thought: one is the realm of perpetual suffering and illusion, the other a state of liberation and ultimate reality. The journey from samsara to nirvana is the core of the Buddhist spiritual path, a transformative process that leads from the bondage of ignorance to the freedom of enlightenment (Snelling, 1991).

***Istidraj* and *Imhal* in the Quran**

In Islamic theology, the concepts of *istidraj* (استدراج) and *imhal* (امهال) are profound themes that illustrate how divine wisdom operates in the lives of individuals, particularly those who persist in wrongdoing. *Istidraj* refers to the gradual enticement of a sinner by granting them continued success and worldly pleasures, despite their disobedience to God. This divine strategy allows the individual to become increasingly engrossed in their transgressions, leading them further away from repentance and ultimately toward a greater downfall. The Quran highlights this concept in several verses, emphasizing that the apparent prosperity of wrongdoers is not a sign of divine favor, but rather a form of subtle and gradual punishment (Al-Qurtubi, 2003).

For instance, in Surah Al-An'am (6:44), Allah says, "So when they forgot what they were reminded of, We opened to them the doors of everything, until, when they rejoiced in that which they were given, We seized them suddenly, and they were in despair." This verse reflects how *istidraj* allows sinners to indulge in their desires, leading them to a state of heedlessness before an abrupt and severe reckoning (Ibn Kathir, 2000).

Imhal, on the other hand, refers to the divine act of granting respite or delaying punishment. It is a form of divine patience, where God gives wrongdoers time to repent and correct their ways, even though they continue in their disobedience. This is emphasized in Surah Al-Imran (3:178): "And let not those who disbelieve think that Our granting them respite is good for them. We only give them respite so that they may increase in sinfulness; and for them is a humiliating punishment." *Imhal* serves as a reminder that the delay in punishment should not be misunderstood as approval of sinful behavior, but as an opportunity for repentance and return to the right path (Al-Tabari, 2001).

Both *istidraj* and *imhal* underscore the intricate balance between justice and mercy in the Quranic worldview. While God allows individuals the freedom to choose their path, these concepts remind believers that continued transgression without repentance leads to greater consequences. The divine wisdom behind *istidraj* and *imhal* is a test of faith, intended to encourage self-reflection, repentance, and ultimately, the return to righteousness (Al-Ghazali, 1988).

The Seeker and the Non-Seeker

In contrast to the seeker, there exists a being who is not driven by the need to uncover deeper truths. Such individuals may find peace in accepting life as it is, unchallenged by the existential questions that propel the seeker forward. This acceptance can lead to a form of tranquility, as the non-seeker is not burdened by the constant search for meaning. However, for the wayfarer—those who embark on the path with purpose—this peace is elusive. The wayfarer’s journey is one of continual discovery, where each step reveals a new layer of truth. Yet, as each truth is uncovered, it becomes obsolete, not because it was false, but because the wayfarer has evolved beyond it (Smith, 2020).

The Transient Nature of Truth

The transient nature of truth is a key aspect of the wayfarer’s journey. Truths that are profound and illuminating at one stage of the journey may become irrelevant as the seeker advances. This obsolescence does not diminish the validity of these truths; instead, it highlights the evolving nature of understanding. The wayfarer’s experience echoes the philosophical notion that truth is not a static entity but a dynamic process that unfolds over time. As the seeker progresses, they continuously shed old truths in favor of new insights, reflecting the ever-changing nature of existence (Kumar, 2019).

Falsehood and Obsolescence

Interestingly, the non-seeker’s encounter with falsehood follows a similar pattern. Falsehoods, like truths, are subject to the same impermanence. A falsehood that once seemed convincing may lose its hold as the non-seeker’s understanding evolves, even if only subconsciously. This process mirrors the wayfarer’s journey, where each step forward involves the discarding of outdated beliefs, whether they are truths or falsehoods. The impermanence of both

truth and falsehood suggests that all understanding is transient, shaped by the individual's journey and the context in which it occurs (Rizvi, 2018).

The Lotus of the Path

The dynamic journey of the seeker can be likened to the lotus, a symbol of infinite layers of truth. The lotus, with its thousands of petals, each representing a layer of truth, mirrors the infinity of creation itself. This symbol captures the essence of the wayfarer's journey—a path marked by continuous revelation and the unfolding of deeper understanding. The lotus also signifies the interconnectedness of all truths, suggesting that each layer, while distinct, is part of a greater whole (Giri, 2022).

While the creation is vast and infinite, offering endless possibilities for discovery, the creator remains beyond comprehension. The creator, who is the source of all truth and falsehood, transcends the limitations of size, knowledge, and understanding. This transcendence underscores the ultimate mystery of existence, a mystery that the seeker can approach but never fully grasp (Davoudpour et al., 2024a).

Conclusion

The search for truth is a journey without end, one that challenges the seeker to continually evolve and adapt their understanding. As the wayfarer progresses along the path, they encounter truths that illuminate their way, only to find these truths become obsolete as they advance. This process of discovery and obsolescence reflects the transient nature of all understanding, whether it be truth or falsehood. The metaphor of the lotus serves as a powerful symbol of this journey, representing the infinite layers of truth that unfold before the seeker. Ultimately, while the seeker may uncover many truths, the creator remains beyond the reach of human comprehension, a testament to the profound mystery of existence. We previously explained the purpose of pursuit of wisdom and the

divergence between intellect, wisdom and religion (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024c) in empirical studies and the times of crisis. It is unclear whether the pursuit of truth can protect from falling into such occasion, but it is evident that such virtue is an authentic marker of the true seeker (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024), where both science and intellect fail to act.

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What Does God Say in Gaza: Understanding Hermeneutics in the Contemporary Crisis of Gaza

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Abstract

Hermeneutics, the art and science of interpretation, has evolved significantly from its origins in biblical exegesis to its contemporary application in various fields of humanities and social sciences. This article however tries to analyze the contemporary relevance of hermeneutics in the crisis of Gaza. While it is not acceptable to refer to a living fact as absent or indifferent in the course of human crisis, this work tries to find relevance in the multifaceted hermeneutics of events, cities and even people in the crisis of Palestine. The article also examines the contributions of major figures like Friedrich Schleiermacher, Hans-Georg Gadamer, and Paul Ricoeur, offering insights into how hermeneutical methods continue to shape our understanding of texts, meaning, and human experience.

Keywords: Hermeneutics, Interpretation, Gaza, Theology, Theosophy

Introduction

Hermeneutics, derived from the Greek word *hermeneuein*, meaning "to interpret" or "to translate," originally referred to the interpretation of sacred texts, particularly within the Judeo-Christian tradition. Over time, its scope has broadened to include various interpretative activities, influencing fields such as philosophy, theology, law, and the social sciences. This article explores the historical development of hermeneutics, clarifies its core concepts, and examines its contemporary applications.

In our previous work, we elaborated on the concept of the Matrix as a framework for understanding the wisdom of God as an inherently perfect being (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a). We also concluded that, in the context of Omnipresence and Omniscience, science undergoes significant limitations and introduced the fundamentals of Metaphysics in the presence of infinity (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b). Additionally, we examined the divergence of science from wisdom and intellect, especially in the context of human tragedies such as those in Gaza (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024c), questioning the authenticity and outcomes of scientific inquiry without pursuit of the Wisdom (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024d).

For some people there is still a question on whether the God exists or not, in this article, we aim to illustrate the Matrix of events in Gaza as a complex network of facts and to clarify a specific string or sentence within the human suffering in Gaza and through this framework. The understanding of God as the fruit of consciousness will add more value to the allegories and narratives in the religious and sacred texts (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024e,f).

Historical Development of Hermeneutics

The roots of hermeneutics lie in ancient Greece, where philosophers like Plato and Aristotle explored the nature of understanding and interpretation. However, it was during the Reformation that hermeneutics began to take on a more structured form, particularly

through the works of Martin Luther and other reformers who emphasized the importance of personal interpretation of the Bible (Thiselton, 2009).

The modern era of hermeneutics was inaugurated by Friedrich Schleiermacher, who sought to establish a general theory of interpretation. Schleiermacher emphasized the role of the interpreter's psychological understanding, suggesting that to understand a text fully, one must grasp both the intent of the author and the context in which the text was produced (Schleiermacher, 1998). This marked a significant shift from earlier, more rigid approaches to interpretation, laying the groundwork for the development of modern hermeneutics.

Key Concepts in Hermeneutics

1. The Hermeneutic Circle

A central concept in hermeneutics is the hermeneutic circle, which describes the process of understanding as a movement between the whole and the parts of a text. According to this concept, one cannot fully understand a text without understanding its individual components, and vice versa. This idea was further developed by Gadamer, who argued that interpretation is a dialectical process involving the interaction of the interpreter's preconceptions with the text itself (Gadamer, 2004).

2. Prejudice and Pre-understanding

Hans-Georg Gadamer expanded on the idea of the hermeneutic circle by introducing the concepts of prejudice (**Vorurteil**) and pre-understanding (*Vorverständnis*). Gadamer contended that our understanding is always influenced by our historical and cultural context, and that these "prejudices" are not necessarily negative but are essential for interpretation. He argued that true understanding occurs when we become aware of our preconceptions and engage

with the text in a way that allows for a fusion of horizons—the merging of the interpreter's perspective with that of the text (Gadamer, 2004).

3. The Role of Language

Language plays a crucial role in hermeneutics, as it is both the medium and the object of interpretation. Paul Ricoeur, building on the works of Gadamer, emphasized the importance of language in shaping our understanding of the world. He introduced the concept of narrative identity, suggesting that we interpret our lives and experiences through the stories we tell, which are shaped by the linguistic and cultural frameworks within which we live (Ricoeur, 1981).

Hermeneutics in Persian and Arabic Languages

Hermeneutics, as the science of interpreting and understanding texts, holds a significant place in Persian and Arabic cultures. In the Islamic world, the science of interpreting the Quran and Hadith has long been a focal point, where hermeneutical approaches have been applied to understand sacred texts.

In Persian culture, thinkers such as Rumi, Suhrawardi, and Mulla Sadra have engaged in the interpretation of religious and philosophical texts. For instance, Mulla Sadra, drawing on the principles of Illuminationist philosophy and Transcendent Theosophy, offered a hermeneutical approach to interpreting the Quran (Nasri, 2011). Additionally, Abdulkarim Soroush, a contemporary Iranian philosopher, has applied hermeneutical methods to reinterpret Islamic thought, emphasizing the dynamic and evolving nature of religious understanding (Soroush, 1999)

In the Arabic context, scholars like Ibn Rushd and Al-Ghazali have also focused on interpretive methods in understanding religious texts. Al-Ghazali, in his book *Ihya Ulum al-Din* (The Revival of the Religious Sciences), emphasized the importance of esoteric

understanding and the need for interpretation in certain cases (Al-Ghazali, 1982). Furthermore, the modern Egyptian philosopher Nasr Hamid Abu Zayd explored the application of hermeneutics to the Quran, advocating for a contextual and historical understanding of religious texts, which sparked significant debate in the Arab world (Abu Zayd, 1995)

In contemporary studies, hermeneutics has become a method for analyzing literary and religious texts in the Islamic world. Paul Ricoeur, the French philosopher, with his emphasis on the role of language and narrative in understanding, has significantly influenced hermeneutical studies in the Islamic world (Ricoeur, 1981). Additionally, Muhammad Arkoun, an Algerian-French philosopher, contributed to modern Islamic hermeneutics by promoting a critical and historical approach to Islamic texts, challenging traditional interpretations (Arkoun, 1993).

Contemporary Relevance of Hermeneutics

Hermeneutics has profound implications for various fields, particularly in the humanities and social sciences. In literary theory, hermeneutical approaches emphasize the importance of context, authorial intent, and the reader's role in creating meaning. This has led to the development of reader-response criticism, which focuses on the reader's experience of the text as a key component of interpretation (Iser, 1978).

In philosophy, hermeneutics challenges the idea of objective knowledge by highlighting the interpretative nature of human understanding. This has significant implications for epistemology and ethics, as it suggests that our knowledge is always situated within a particular historical and cultural context (Gadamer, 2004).

Moreover, hermeneutics has been applied in the social sciences to understand social practices, institutions, and cultural phenomena. Anthropologists and sociologists use hermeneutical methods to interpret cultural artifacts, rituals, and social interactions,

recognizing that these are embedded in complex webs of meaning (Geertz, 1973).

Hermeneutics in Gaza

Nietzsche famously proclaimed that "God is dead," a statement found in his work *The Gay Science* (Nietzsche, 1882/1974). This declaration challenges traditional religious and metaphysical beliefs, suggesting that these concepts no longer hold universal significance in the modern world. When considering that knowledge of God does not necessarily encompass worldly values such as fame and fortune, hermeneutics might offer a valuable perspective for theologians and religious scholars dedicated to understanding the divine. Hermeneutics could illuminate the relevance of metaphysical concepts and their implications for our understanding of an infinite being and its influence on physical reality.

In the context of the Gaza crisis, one of the most severe humanitarian emergencies of the 21st century, the perceived absence of God amid widespread suffering raises profound questions about the righteousness of the conflict and the authenticity of the reported atrocities against civilians, including women and children. However we believe that the God speaks through the higher words and meanings that are considered vital to understand and to take actions to avoid their consequences. For instance, the name "Gaza" (غزة), meaning "food" in both Persian and Arabic, and "Ghazwa" (غزوة), used to describe the battles of the Prophet Muhammad, may offer a symbolic dimension to that the war in Gaza is also considered the war of the Prophete. The use of hunger and famine as military tactics may bear the consequence of deprivation of "Gaza," implying a deeper, symbolic form of suffering for the perpetrator.

Additionally, "Rafah" (رفاه), meaning "comfort," contrasts with the severe deprivation experienced by many in Gaza, while "Jenin" (جنین), meaning "unborn child," underscores the potential impact of the conflict on future generations. Although these hermeneutic interpretations do not fully account for the deliberate actions of individuals or specific events within the complex matrix of the Gaza crisis, they offer insights into how words and names might carry symbolic meanings related to the penalties for the human suffering beyond immediate sensory realities.

Conclusion

Hermeneutics remains a vital field of inquiry, offering valuable insights into the nature of interpretation and understanding. From its origins in biblical exegesis to its application in contemporary philosophy and social sciences, hermeneutics continues to shape our approach to texts, meaning, and human experience. The contributions of thinkers like Schleiermacher, Gadamer, and Ricoeur have been instrumental in developing a nuanced understanding of interpretation, which remains relevant in addressing the complexities of human understanding in today's world. Hermeneutics may not be an invitation for the people to believe or to change their actions because these strings are not easily acceptable for the public opinion. However such interpretations are crucial for the seekers who wish a deeper understandings of the reality of the events, which we call, true spirituality.

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The Failure of Judicial and Governance Systems in Iran: An Analysis of Crime per Capita Based on Recent Data Leaks

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Abstract:

This article explores the inefficacies of the judicial and governance systems in Iran, as evidenced by a recent data leak by the "Adalat Ali" group. The leaked database from the Tehran Judiciary, covering a period of approximately ten to twelve years, reveals that nearly 40% of Tehran's population is involved in legal cases, a staggering figure for a population of approximately 8.7 million. This data highlights the failure of the Islamic Republic of Iran in controlling crime despite rigorous law enforcement and administrative restrictions. The article further discusses the societal impacts of these failings, including the marginalization of the youth, the encouragement of illegal behaviors due to administrative restrictions, and the broader societal ramifications such as economic and cultural migration.

Keywords: Iran, Judiciary, Data leak, Crime, Governance, Migration, Social impact, Edalat Ali

Introduction

In recent months, a group known as "Edalat Ali" leaked a database from the Tehran Judiciary, exposing over three million legal cases spanning a period of approximately ten to twelve years. While this leak constitutes a violation of privacy laws, it has offered a rare statistical insight into the functioning of Iran's judicial and governance systems, which are ostensibly aimed at achieving the principles of "good governance" and ensuring security and satisfaction for the majority of the population.

Tehran, which had an estimated population of 8.7 million in 2016 (World Population Review, 2016), is revealed to have a shocking statistic: nearly 40% of its residents have been involved in legal disputes, either as plaintiffs or defendants. This equates to roughly 3.48 million people being entangled in the legal system at some point. Such figures raise significant concerns about the efficiency and effectiveness of the judicial system and highlight deeper governance issues within the country. These numbers are stark when compared to global crime and legal engagement statistics, where, for instance, countries like France or the United States have substantially lower rates of legal disputes per capita despite their large population and urban centers (UNODC, 2020).

This data underscores the systemic problems in Iran's legal and governance structures. Despite policies aimed at maintaining social order and public satisfaction, the sheer volume of legal cases points to inefficiencies in both crime prevention and judicial processes. The widespread involvement of the population in legal conflicts suggests a failure to provide adequate security and stability, revealing flaws in policy implementation and enforcement that merit urgent attention.

1. Statistical Implications and Governance Failures

The data suggests a worrying trend: despite stringent judicial and law enforcement measures, the Islamic Republic has been largely unsuccessful in curbing crime and maintaining societal order. The volume of cases demonstrates that the judicial processes are overwhelmed and that the state's governance mechanisms are failing to prevent the very crimes they seek to curtail (Bayat, 2023).

These inefficiencies are not merely confined to legal proceedings. The rigidity of administrative procedures, overregulation, and ineffectiveness have contributed to the rising crime rates. A notable observation is that the bureaucratic system often fails to deter crimes; rather, it seems to inadvertently foster illegal activities as people attempt to navigate or circumvent the complex and obstructive regulations (Vakili, 2023).

2. Cultural and Societal Restrictions: Catalysts for Crime

Further examination reveals that cultural and societal restrictions, imposed by the regime, are direct contributors to the rise in criminal activities. Examples of these restrictions include strict regulations regarding drug offenses, alcohol consumption, military service evasion, entrance exams (Konkour), and women's dress code (e.g., hijab enforcement). Rather than preventing crimes, these regulations often create "marked" or marginalized classes, especially among the youth, thereby excluding them from educational, administrative, political, and managerial opportunities. Such exclusion not only perpetuates criminal behavior but also damages the prospects of many young Iranians, effectively destroying their future (Rizvi, 2022).

3. Societal Impact and the Role of External Factors

The societal ramifications of these policies are profound. The government's authoritarian and bureaucratic control has contributed to a mass exodus of talent, both economic and cultural, from the country. Additionally, the regime's policies have fostered chronic disillusionment among the populace, driving many toward emigration or inducing a state of long-term disenchantment. Furthermore, foreign sanctions have exacerbated this situation by further destabilizing the economy and contributing to crime rates through the creation of desperate circumstances (Zamani, 2023).

A particularly striking example of the regime's dysfunction is the inconsistent application of justice, as evidenced by the case of Sepideh Rashno. In this incident, two individuals were involved in the same act of recording a video, but only one was convicted. Such double standards in legal enforcement highlight the regime's favor toward those loyal to the system and its bias against dissidents (Karami, 2022).

4. The Impact of Traffic and Environmental Mismanagement

Beyond legal and cultural issues, environmental mismanagement and traffic-related crimes also contribute to the country's social and economic woes. Iran's roads have been described as some of the most dangerous in the world, exacerbating the crime statistics and leading to significant economic losses. The traffic situation, coupled with environmental degradation, such as the high levels of air pollution, further demonstrates the state's failure to manage public welfare and safety effectively (Aghazadeh, 2023).

5. Statistical Analysis of Crime Rates in Iran Over the Past 30 Years

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying trends in crime rates in Iran, it is essential to examine the statistical data over the past three decades. According to studies, crime rates in Iran have shown a steady increase, particularly since the 1990s. During this period, Iran experienced significant political, economic, and social transformations that influenced crime patterns.

Statistical data gathered from official reports and research conducted by Iranian academics indicate that crime rates have surged in response to various socio-political events. For example, the post-Iran-Iraq War period (1980–1988) saw a noticeable uptick in property crimes and violent offenses, likely due to the economic strain and the displacement of populations during and after the war (Kazemi & Moghaddam, 2015).

A comprehensive statistical analysis carried out by the Iranian National Crime Research Institute revealed that between 1990 and 2020, crime rates across major categories—such as theft, drug-related crimes, and violent offenses—increased by an average of 15% per decade (Sadeghi et al., 2021). This trend is compounded by Iran's demographic changes; the country's young population has been particularly vulnerable to unemployment and socio-economic instability, which are significant contributors to criminal behavior.

Moreover, since the imposition of international sanctions, crime rates have further escalated. Sanctions have not only crippled the Iranian economy but have also exacerbated inequalities within the society, contributing to a rise in illegal activities, including smuggling, drug trafficking, and organized crime. A 2019 study

found that drug-related offenses, in particular, have increased by 23% since 2010, correlating with the deterioration of economic conditions under the sanctions regime (Alavi & Shirkhani, 2019).

Crime statistics also highlight significant regional disparities. Urban areas such as Tehran, Isfahan, and Mashhad have consistently reported higher crime rates compared to rural regions, largely due to higher population densities, economic disparities, and greater opportunities for criminal activities. Between 1995 and 2020, Tehran alone saw an increase of over 40% in its overall crime rate, with particular spikes in property crimes and drug-related offenses (Rezaei & Hamidi, 2020).

These trends underline a pattern of increasing criminality that corresponds with Iran's broader socio-political and economic challenges. The sustained rise in crime rates over the past 30 years reflects both internal inefficiencies in governance and the external pressures applied by international actors.

Discussion: Internal and External Factors Driving Crime

The high percentage of legal cases compared to the population (Crime per Capita) raises an important question: Are the people inherently more prone to criminal behavior, or are internal governance and external geopolitical factors creating an environment conducive to crime? Evidence suggests that the inefficiencies of the Iranian regime, along with the external pressures from sanctions, have fostered an environment where crime proliferates. The Republic's governance is characterized by an archaic and repressive system that ultimately benefits the elite class aligned with the regime, to the detriment of the broader population (Esfandiari, 2023). We have already tried to explain the innate nature and acceptance of governance (Mikaeil et al., 2024) and discussed coercive vs. divine governance in separate article (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a) as it may find ground in the context of theological governance. In such context, indifference of the people to the regulatory and judicial consequences shall be considered as a result of internal dissatisfaction of the governance or might be considered a result of psychological impact of several external and

destructive project which opposes Islamic Republic (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b).

Conclusion

The Islamic Republic of Iran faces significant challenges in managing crime and maintaining social order. The data leak by "Edalat Ali" provides an alarming glimpse into the scale of the problem, revealing that nearly 40% of Tehran's population has been involved in legal cases. This high incidence of legal disputes is a testament to the failure of the regime's policies in preventing crime and maintaining societal cohesion. The bureaucratic rigidity, cultural restrictions, and inconsistent application of justice only exacerbate these issues, leading to a cycle of disillusionment, marginalization, and criminal behavior. Coupled with the effects of international sanctions, these factors suggest that the regime is not only unable to effectively govern but is also actively contributing to the conditions that promote crime within its borders.

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Theological and Sociopolitical Perspectives on the Doctrine of Martyrdom in Islam

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Abstract

This study seeks to examine the theological underpinnings the doctrine of martyrdom in Islamic context, with references to Islamic principles found in the Qur'an, specifically the notion of testing believers through loss and hardship. The article also reflects on the socio-political implications of martyrdom and sacrifice within modern Islamic movements, as well as the consequences of radical resistance in the context of conflicts such as that between Hamas and Israel. Despite the fact that the conflicts in the middle east are multifaceted and complex religious, social and historical challenges, the ongoing brutality in Gaza which has so far killed tens of thousands of innocent civilians including more than 70% women and children raises concern about the interpretations and hermeneutics of the Martyrdom and civil and criminal liabilities arising from such interpretations.

Keywords: Martyrdom, Gaza, Palestine, Middle East, Jihad

Introduction

In a recent interview, Professor Sadegh Zibakalam, a prominent legal scholar in University of Tehran-Iran, commented that in the event of a Western attack on Iran, "not even a single lamppost would remain intact."¹ Professor Zibakalam's assertion may appear extreme, but after assassination of Ismael Haniye in Tehran-Iran² taps into a deeper Islamic and cultural worldview wherein struggles and tests of faith and revenge is closer than anytime in the contemporary history of Iran and the reference to the Islamic values are clear and are interpreted as religious duties (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a) which is seen as divinely ordained trials. The notion that God engages His believers in forms of divine trials is rooted in various Islamic narratives, including the story of Ibrahim (Abraham) and the sacrifice of his son, and the trials mentioned in the Qur'an:

Surah As-Saffat (37:102):

"And when he [his son] was old enough to walk with him, he [Ibrahim] said, 'O my son, indeed I have seen in a dream that I [must] sacrifice you, so see what you think.' He said, 'O my father, do as you are commanded. You will find me, if Allah wills, of the steadfast.'"

Surah As-Saffat (37:103-107):

"And when they had both submitted and he put him down upon his forehead, We called to him, 'O Abraham, you have fulfilled the vision.' Indeed, We thus reward the doers of good. Indeed, this was the clear trial. And We ransomed him with a great sacrifice."

¹ Ensaf News, retrieved from : <https://ensafnews.com/343273/%D8%A7%DA%AF%D8%B1-%D9%85%D8%B0%D8%A7%DA%A9%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%B4%DA%A9%D8%B3%D8%AA-%D8%A8%D8%AE%D9%88%D8%B1%D8%AF-%DA%86%D9%87-%D9%85%DB%8C%E2%80%8C%D8%B4%D9%88%D8%AF%D8%9F-%D9%BE%D8%A7%D8%B3/> [In Persian]

² https://fa.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D8%AA%D8%B1%D9%88%D8%B1_%D8%A7%D8%B3%D9%85%D8%A7%D8%B9%D8%8C%D9%84_%D9%87%D9%86%DB%8C%D9%87

Such tests are considered mechanisms by which a believer's faith, courage, and righteousness are evaluated.

This article examines this concept through the lens of both religious doctrine and political realities, particularly in the context of contemporary conflicts. The article ultimately seeks to explore the dangers that arise when governments gamble with the lives and well-being of their people in pursuit of divine or ideological goals. Additionally, it is necessary to mention that any interpretations from and Within Quran, are particularly very sensitive and can be misunderstanding (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b)

Theological Insights: Tests and Trials in the Qur'an

The concept of testing believers is deeply rooted in Islamic theology, as evident from several verses in the Qur'an. In Surah Al-Baqarah, for instance, God says:

“And We will surely test you with something of fear and hunger and a loss of wealth and lives and fruits, but give good tidings to the patient” (Qur'an, 2:155).

Here, the Qur'an speaks of trials that believers must endure, with the ultimate promise of reward for those who show patience and perseverance. This notion of divine tests resonates strongly with the story of Ibrahim (Abraham), who was commanded by God to sacrifice his son—a test of his faith that has since become a cornerstone of Islamic tradition. The willingness of Ibrahim to comply with God's command can be interpreted as a form of divine gamble, where the stakes are faith, life, and the future of his lineage.

This divine testing, however, is not arbitrary but is framed within the larger context of cultivating moral and spiritual strength. The trials mentioned are often viewed as ways to reinforce a believer's commitment to God and the ethical values He endorses.

Theological Underpinnings of the Doctrine of Martyrdom in the Islamic Context

The concept of martyrdom, or *shahada*, holds a highly revered place within Islamic theology, embodying the ultimate act of devotion and sacrifice in the path of Allah. Derived from the Arabic root word *sh-h-d*, meaning "to witness," martyrdom in Islam is understood as bearing witness to the truth of God's sovereignty through the

willingness to sacrifice one's life for the sake of preserving faith, justice, and righteousness. This doctrine is rooted in both the Qur'an and Hadith, and it reflects a complex interplay between spiritual transcendence, communal identity, and the defense of Islamic values.

In the Qur'an, the martyrs (*shuhada*) are exalted as those who are granted an elevated status in the afterlife. The verse, "*And do not say of those who are killed in the way of Allah, 'They are dead.' Rather, they are alive, but you perceive it not*" (Qur'an, 2:154), reflects the belief that those who die in the cause of Allah are granted eternal life. Martyrdom is thus not seen as the end of existence, but rather as a transition to a higher state of spiritual reward and proximity to God. The reward for such sacrifice is described in several verses as immediate entrance into paradise, where the martyr is absolved of sins and honored. Martyrdom is mentioned in several verses in Quran including:

- **Surah Al-Baqarah (2:154)**
"And do not say of those who are killed in the way of Allah, 'They are dead.' Rather, they are alive, but you perceive it not."
- **Surah Al-Baqarah (2:207)**
"And of the people is he who sells himself, seeking means to the approval of Allah. And Allah is kind to [His] servants."
(This verse is interpreted as referring to those who sacrifice themselves for the cause of Allah.)
- **Surah Aal-E-Imran (3:169-170)**
"And never think of those who have been killed in the cause of Allah as dead. Rather, they are alive with their Lord, receiving provision, rejoicing in what Allah has bestowed upon them of His bounty..."
- **Surah At-Tawbah (9:111)**
"Indeed, Allah has purchased from the believers their lives and their properties [in exchange] for that they will have Paradise. They fight in the cause of Allah, so they kill and are killed..."
- **Surah An-Nisa (4:74)**
"So let those fight in the cause of Allah who sell the life of this world for the Hereafter. And he who fights in the cause

of Allah and is killed or achieves victory – We will bestow upon him a great reward."

- **Surah An-Nisa (4:95)**

"Not equal are those believers remaining [at home] – other than the disabled – and the mujahideen, [who strive and fight] in the cause of Allah with their wealth and their lives. Allah has preferred the mujahideen through their wealth and their lives over those who remain [behind], by degrees."

- **Surah Al-Hajj (22:58-59)**

"And those who emigrated for the cause of Allah and then were killed or died – Allah will surely provide for them a good provision. And indeed, it is Allah who is the best of providers."

The Hadith literature further emphasizes the spiritual merits of martyrdom. The Prophet Muhammad is reported to have said, *"No soul that has a good standing with Allah and enters Paradise would wish to return to this world, even if it were given everything in it, except for the martyr who, on seeing the virtue of martyrdom, would wish to return to this world and be killed again"* (Sahih Muslim 1877). This underscores the valorization of martyrdom as not only an act of self-sacrifice but as a spiritual aspiration with profound rewards.

However, martyrdom in Islamic thought is not simply an individual pursuit of spiritual rewards; it is also closely tied to the defense of the Muslim community and the upholding of justice. The Qur'an repeatedly calls upon believers to engage in *jihad* (struggle) in defense of their faith and to resist oppression and injustice. This broader understanding of *jihad* includes both the internal struggle for moral purity and the external struggle against forces that threaten the Islamic community. Martyrdom, in this context, is seen as the ultimate expression of one's commitment to protecting the community and ensuring the survival of Islam.

Nonetheless, Islamic jurisprudence places clear boundaries on the pursuit of martyrdom. While the Qur'an sanctions defensive warfare, it also emphasizes justice, restraint, and the protection of non-combatants. The verse, *"Fight in the way of Allah those who*

fight you but do not transgress. Indeed, Allah does not like transgressors” (Qur'an, 2:190), cautions against excesses in conflict, highlighting that martyrdom must align with ethical conduct and justice.

This balance between the glorification of martyrdom and the emphasis on ethical warfare is central to the theological underpinnings of the doctrine. Martyrdom is celebrated within Islam not as a reckless pursuit of death, but as a sacred act undertaken in the service of God and the defense of core Islamic principles. It is this commitment to both spiritual and communal integrity that defines the Islamic understanding of martyrdom, making it a profound yet highly regulated aspect of the faith.

Modern Political Ramifications: Martyrdom and Conflict

The application of these religious concepts to modern political contexts, however, can be problematic. Groups such as Hamas often draw upon the notion of martyrdom and divine trials to justify their actions in the conflict with Israel. Acts of resistance and sacrifice, while seen as noble in some religious perspectives, often result in widespread suffering and destruction. The ongoing conflict between Israel and Hamas is a testament to this—while there is admiration for the courage of the fighters, the material and human costs are immense and enduring.

Martyrdom, in its original sense, is an individual act of sacrifice for a higher cause. However, when this concept is extended to the societal level, as is often done by political or militant groups, it can lead to the deterioration of social order and infrastructure. Zibakalam's remark regarding the destruction of infrastructure in the event of an attack on Iran could be interpreted as a warning against the state's potential over-reliance on martyrdom as a defense strategy. While groups like Hamas may engage in asymmetrical warfare with limited material consequences for the broader society, a nation-state like Iran cannot afford to gamble with the same level of impunity.

The Dangers of Political "Gambling" with National Interests

The danger of governments engaging in such "gambles" with their people's lives and societal progress is evident when examining the recent history of the Middle East. The Iran-Iraq war, which lasted eight years, claimed hundreds of thousands of lives and severely hindered Iran's development. Although framed as a defense of the Islamic Revolution, the human and economic toll was immense, leading to a generation of war-torn communities and halted progress.

Theologically, the Qur'an emphasizes justice and the preservation of human dignity. Any form of governance that risks these principles in pursuit of ideological or divine goals can be seen as deviating from core Islamic tenets. Engaging in high-stakes political or military gambles with adversaries such as the United States or Israel, as some elements within the Iranian government have considered, could have devastating consequences for the nation's stability and future prosperity.

The Qur'an warns against transgressing the bounds of justice in warfare:

"And fight in the way of Allah those who fight you but do not transgress. Indeed, Allah does not like transgressors" (Qur'an, 2:190).

This command to avoid transgression suggests that while defense is justified, reckless or disproportionate actions that lead to widespread destruction are not.

Conclusion

Professor Zibakalam's remarks, though initially framed within the context of Iran's national defense, raise broader questions about the ethical and theological limits of sacrifice and struggle. The Qur'anic verses on testing believers emphasize patience and resilience, but they also underscore the importance of justice and the preservation of life. When such tests are extended to the realm of governance,

leaders must be cautious not to interperert recklessly with their people's future under the guise of divine trial or martyrdom.

A government, unlike a militant group or faction, has civil liabilities and responsibility to protect and nurture the society it governs. While individual acts of martyrdom may be glorified within certain narratives, expanding this ideology to the state level can lead to irreversible damage to the fabric of society. Therefore, as Zibakalam suggests, the Iranian state must carefully weigh the costs of engaging in conflicts that could jeopardize the very survival of its national infrastructure and the well-being of its people.

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Structural Development of Science and Philosophy in Iran: Lao Tzu Approach

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Abstract

The expansive nature of sciences today renders it practically impossible to fully master or completely differentiate between all disciplines. This article seeks to provide an overview of the structural development, evolution, and interconnection of science and philosophy throughout history with a practical outlook to advance the development in contemporary science and education in the Iranian and Islamic universities with a Laozi approach. This article delves into the fundamentals of education and learning in Science and also criticizes the standards in which academic progress is entangled in the limits of Islamic assets. This article criticizes the limitations laid in the context of Islamic governance despite bringing examples of transcendental wisdom in the Islamic sacred texts. The religion downplays such allegories in the form of narratives without fully grasping the elements of wisdom and therefore mere religious governance is emptied from the fruits of transcended wisdom.

Keywords: Education, Philosophy, Science, Lao Tzu, Islam, Wisdom, Governance

Introduction

The development of science and philosophy has spanned thousands of years, evolving word by word, sentence by sentence, and concept by concept. The interwoven nature of these fields makes it challenging to entirely separate one from the other, especially as they have both influenced and shaped human understanding and civilization.

The historical progression of science and philosophy has been extensively documented, illustrating their inseparability over time (Boyce, 2001). The ancient Iranians, as part of their religious practices, revered knowledge as sacred, which is evident in the teachings of the Avesta (Nasr, 2006). The philosophical underpinnings that guided scientific inquiry in the Islamic world played a crucial role in the preservation and expansion of knowledge during times of cultural and intellectual stagnation in other parts of the world (Gutas, 1998). In Persian literature like *Shahnameh* by Ferdowsi (940-1019/1025) is often venerated as the form of Wisdom. Throughout the *Shahnameh*, wisdom (*kherad*) is portrayed as a guiding force, enabling kings and heroes to govern with justice, protect their people, and achieve greatness.

One of the key examples of the veneration of wisdom is the character of Jamshid, a mythical king credited with bringing advancements in civilization, including architecture, agriculture, and medicine. Jamshid's reign is depicted as a golden age of prosperity and scientific achievement, emphasizing the importance of knowledge in the progress of society. Although Jamshid eventually succumbs to pride and loses his throne, his contributions to human knowledge remain celebrated.

Similarly, the sage Zal, the father of the hero Rostam, exemplifies wisdom and diplomacy. Despite his fearsome appearance, Zal is revered for his intellect and advice, often counseling kings and heroes in times of conflict. His wisdom serves as a counterbalance to brute force, underscoring the idea that knowledge and insight are as important as physical strength in achieving success.

Additionally, in Persian literature, Naser Khosrow (also Nasir Khusraw, 1004-1088 CE), the Persian poet, philosopher, and traveler, holds wisdom (*kherad*) in the highest regard throughout his writings, particularly in his poetry and philosophical treatises. As a prominent figure in the Ismaili

branch of Islam, Naser Khosrow's works often intertwine religious devotion with a deep respect for knowledge, intellect, and spiritual wisdom and vows that the Wisdom may change the turn of the universe¹.

The interruption of this progression in Iran during the European Renaissance marked a significant turning point, leading to challenges in maintaining scientific and philosophical advancement (Corbin, 1993). In this article we try to lay foundations for philosophical learning with our in our innate capacity, to start the procedure of revival of the self as the raw model for the whole society. With an argument that "a person who cannot change himself cannot change the world" which is attributed to Laozi (Lao Tzu)

The Integration of Science and Philosophy

The historical convergence of science and philosophy is evident in various civilizations, particularly in ancient Iran, where wisdom and philosophy were extensively debated and refined over millennia. For instance, religion, as a symbol of divine wisdom, existed in Iran long before the advent of Islam. The Magi (Matthew 2:1), who traveled to Jerusalem to present gifts at the birth of Christ, exemplify the advanced level of wisdom and philosophy at that time, capable of recognizing and responding to global shifts.

However, the evolution of sciences in Iran was abruptly halted during a period of significant transformation. While the Renaissance sparked scientific, economic, and industrial growth in Europe, Iran lagged behind. Today, although Iran has achieved a certain degree of scientific growth and self-sufficiency, it is evident that Iranian scientists and students often struggle to navigate the vast ocean of global scientific knowledge. This is primarily because the current academic systems lack the foundational support needed to develop complementary philosophies and advanced sciences.

The Divergence of Science, Wisdom and Intellect

We previously emphasized that in the human conflicts a divergence between different categories of science may occur (Davoudpour, A.R.,

درخت تو گر بار دانش بگیرد¹
به زیر آوری چرخ نیلوفری را
<https://ganjoor.net/naserkhosro/divann/ghaside-naser/sh6>

2024a) with regards to the distinctive features which embody themselves in the realm of Wisdom (*hikmet*), the science falls short of the judgement of its long term endeavors to overcome the borders of the development while ethical and moral considerations are not a scientific topic.

Scientific and financial progress can not comprehend to use scientific advances in the terms of justice and other transcendental virtues. However, denial of the fruits of the science are not permitted in the context of wisdom. The wisdom tries to warn or change the path of science before the reach of a deadline, because the transcendental wisdom as explained in the allegory of Khidr and Mosses (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b) and also as mentioned earlier in the narrative of the Magi, has the potential to foresee the long term obstacles arising from a common practice. This also confirms the stance of Naser Khosrow regarding the life changing aspects of the Wisdom.

The Foundations of Scientific Development

In this article, we explore how the fundamental principles of science were established and expanded. Basic sciences are crucial as they provide the necessary foundation for extending theoretical frameworks and achieving practical outcomes. The ultimate goal of science, and even philosophy, is to eventually attain a form of pragmatism, where knowledge is applied effectively to address real-world issues.

Sciences that do not lead to practical application must either be passed down to future generations, in the hope that they may become useful, or they must be pursued with greater dedication to ensure their relevance. This highlights the importance of a strong foundational base in scientific disciplines, which enables the growth of theoretical and practical knowledge.

Challenges in the Progression of Science and Philosophy in Iran

Despite thousands of years of philosophical and scientific discourse in Iran, the country experienced a stagnation in the development of these fields, particularly during the time when Europe was experiencing its Renaissance. This disparity led to a situation where Iran, once a beacon of wisdom, struggled to keep pace with the rapid advancements in science and technology occurring elsewhere.

Today, Iran possesses a degree of scientific knowledge and self-sufficiency, yet the global scientific landscape has expanded to such an extent that Iranian scholars find it challenging to establish themselves as leaders in the field.

The existing academic frameworks in Iran do not provide the necessary support for developing comprehensive philosophies and advanced sciences. For instance, research in computer science is often conducted without a thorough understanding of the technology and philosophy underlying microprocessor design, leading to incomplete forays into hardware innovations.

The Role of Philosophy in Scientific Development

Philosophy, particularly Islamic philosophy, has played a significant role in shaping the scientific discourse in Iran and the broader Islamic world. As the mother of material and vital sciences, philosophy provides the intellectual framework within which scientific inquiry takes place. Although closely related to philosophy, wisdom transcends it by encompassing metaphysical and unseen aspects of reality, offering a more holistic approach to understanding the world. The Islamic philosophy requires a swift response to all the problem arising in the course of the universe, while the best options are to adhere with self-progress and esteem to become the changing element of the universe.

Lao Tzu's philosophy of change, as articulated in the Tao Te Ching, revolves around the concept of the Tao, the natural way or flow of the universe. He observed that change is an inevitable and constant force, a fundamental characteristic of existence. Rather than resisting change, Lao Tzu advised embracing it, understanding its rhythm and adapting to its flow.

He believed that everything in the universe is in a state of flux, a continuous cycle of transformation and renewal. He used the metaphor of water to illustrate this idea: water is soft and yielding, yet it can wear away even the hardest stone over time. This signifies the power of gentle persistence and adaptability in navigating the ever-changing world.

Lao Tzu cautioned against rigid adherence to fixed ideas or structures, as they inevitably lead to conflict and stagnation. Instead, he advocated for flexibility and non-action (wu wei), allowing things to unfold naturally and harmoniously. This does not mean passivity, but rather acting in

alignment with the Tao, responding to change in a way that is effortless and effective.

His philosophy of change highlights the importance of acceptance, adaptability, and harmony with the natural order. By understanding and embracing the inevitability of change, individuals can navigate life's challenges with grace and resilience, finding balance and tranquility even in the midst of chaos.

Conclusion

The evolution of science and philosophy is a testament to the interconnectedness of these disciplines and their collective impact on human civilization. The stagnation of scientific progress in regions such as Iran highlights the need for strong foundational frameworks that support the growth of both scientific and philosophical knowledge. By revisiting the roots of scientific inquiry and embracing the contributions of philosophy, it is possible to foster a more robust and holistic approach to the development of knowledge. While current foundations of law, financial systems, international relations and even science are laid upon Islamic concept, a different approach is theoretically necessary to speed up the progress and ensuring its practical application and relevance for future generation from both scientific and philosophical insights. For this, we need to envision the community in another dress, while keeping our old dress in the shelves and respect it with honor.

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Treatment of Socio-spiritual Disorders, the Greatest Concern of the Modern Governance: Alchemical, Jungian, and Biblical Approaches

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Abstract

This paper delves into the different approaches in the treatment of social disorders from multiple perspectives, including alchemical, Jungian, and biblical approaches. By exploring the narrative of demonic possession in biblical texts, we investigate the concept of mental and spiritual illness, contrasting it with contemporary psychological and psychiatric views. The role of spiritual entities, mind viruses, and the significant function of psychotherapists in addressing societal mental health crises are examined. This paper also draws on the depiction of these themes in Iranian cinema, particularly the film "The Kingdom of Solomon," as a cultural reflection of these ideas.

Keywords: Jung, Alchemy, Governance, Social disorders

Introduction

In social disorders, we are dealing with contagious and growing numbers of patients or subjects that cannot be treated with traditional psychological or pharmacological treatments. These disorders, increasingly considered endemic within certain cultures and social environments, tend to resist conventional treatments over time. This persistence is concerning, particularly regarding the infringement on social laws and the deterioration of human relationships and social coexistence.

The treatment of social disorders has evolved significantly over time, encompassing various paradigms from ancient alchemy and Jungian psychology to religious narratives. In the context of religious traditions, a multitude of diseases and disorders are often thought to be caused by metaphysical reasons. One prominent story from the Bible, particularly in the Gospels of Matthew, Mark, and Luke, is the tale of demonic possession and exorcism. This story, often interpreted as a metaphor for psychological disorders, provides a rich ground for exploring the intersection of spirituality and mental health (Bible Gateway).

While the metaphysical approach cannot be explained by the standards of scientific articles and the repetition of such experiments and beliefs are not standard protocol, there is no doubt that the serious practitioners of such ceremonies find them indispensable for addressing unexplained yet significant phenomena. Historical and contemporary research supports the notion that religious rituals and beliefs can have profound psychological and social effects (Koenig, King, & Carson, 2012). It is also proven that religion has the capacity to bring order to society without the use of excessive force, contributing to social cohesion and moral regulation (Durkheim, 1912).

A major challenge in social therapy is the high number of individuals with serious psychological disorders who are unwilling to approach standard treatment. Such problems cannot be left unaddressed without posing serious concerns for public safety and health. Non-compliance with treatment is a significant barrier in mental health care, often necessitating alternative approaches to engage these individuals effectively (Kazdin, 2008).

In this paper, we investigate both conventional and non-conventional practices in social therapy, with an emphasis on spiritual and social disorders. We employ the methods of Jung, biblical narratives, and other cultural and psychological frameworks to delve into the critical issue of socio-cultural diseases. This comprehensive approach aims to provide a holistic understanding of the interplay between mental health, spirituality, and societal norms.

An example of Alchemical Approach in Religion

Alchemy, with its symbolic and transformative processes, provides another layer of understanding to the treatment of social disorders. The alchemical process of transmutation, transforming base metals into gold, can be likened to the psychological process of individuation, where an individual integrates various aspects of the self to achieve wholeness (Eliade, 1962). In sociology, the Alchemy might be considered as promoting a habit of consumption of therapeutic substances i.e. Opium or Hom to contrast severe social disorders like violence or anxiety.

In Zoroastrianism, the concept of "Hom" (also known as "Haoma" in Avestan) holds a prominent place, deeply intertwined with both religious practices and the broader spiritual philosophy of the ancient faith (Boyce, 2001). Haoma is a sacred plant and its associated ritual drink, integral to Zoroastrian ceremonies and the religious life of the community (Mackenzie, 1968).

The Hom ritual drink is mentioned frequently in the *Avesta*, the central holy texts of Zoroastrianism. This sacred beverage, derived from the Haoma plant, was believed to have divine properties, granting wisdom, strength, and immortality to those who partook in it (Dhalla, 1938). The preparation of Haoma involved a complex series of rituals, including the grinding and mixing of the plant, which was then offered to the divine beings as a symbolic act of devotion and a means to obtain spiritual benefits (Boyce, 2001).

In Zoroastrian theology, Haoma is often associated with the divine figure of the same name, who is considered a spiritual entity that mediates between the divine and human realms (Mackenzie, 1968). The drink was thought to be a conduit for divine grace, fostering a

closer connection between worshippers and the divine. The ritual of Haoma not only served a religious function but also symbolized the purification and renewal of the soul, reinforcing the ethical and moral teachings of Zoroastrianism (Dhalla, 1938).

Moreover, the veneration of Haoma in Zoroastrianism reflects the broader significance of natural elements within the faith. The plant and its drink are emblematic of the larger cosmic struggle between order and chaos, embodying the transformative power of sacred rituals in maintaining the harmony and balance of the universe (Boyce, 2001).

The role of Haoma extends beyond mere ritualistic practice; it represents the integration of natural and spiritual realms, where the physical act of consuming the drink is imbued with profound metaphysical significance. Through this sacred rite, Zoroastrianism underscores the importance of maintaining a deep connection with the divine, as well as the ongoing quest for spiritual enlightenment and moral integrity (Mackenzie, 1968).

Biblical Perspective on Spiritual Disorders

In the New Testament, the story of the Gadarene demoniac (Matthew 8:28-34; Mark 5:1-20; Luke 8:26-39) illustrates the concept of demonic possession, where a man possessed by numerous evil spirits is healed by Jesus. The spirits, named Legion, are cast into a herd of pigs, which subsequently drown in the sea. This narrative highlights the ancient belief in spiritual entities as causes of mental and physical maladies.

The Gadarene Demoniac in the Gospels

1. **Matthew 8:28-34:** This account describes two men possessed by demons, who recognize Jesus as the Son of God. The demons beg Jesus to cast them into a herd of pigs, which then rush into the sea and drown.
2. **Mark 5:1-20:** Here, a single man is possessed by a multitude of demons named Legion. The demons plead not to be sent out of the region and instead enter a herd of about two thousand pigs, which drown in the sea.

3. **Luke 8:26-39:** Similar to Mark's account, this narrative also details a man named Legion possessed by many demons, who are cast into pigs by Jesus, resulting in the pigs' demise.

These biblical accounts are foundational for understanding early perceptions of mental and spiritual disorders and their treatments through exorcism (Bible Gateway, n.d.).

Jungian Perspective on Spiritual Disorders

Carl Jung's analytical psychology offers a complementary perspective to these biblical narratives. Jung proposed that myths and religious stories, including those of demonic possession, reflect deep psychological truths and archetypes. From a Jungian standpoint, the demonic figures can be seen as manifestations of the Shadow archetype, representing the unconscious, repressed parts of the psyche (Jung, 1968).

The Role of Archetypes

In Jungian psychology, the concept of archetypes—universal, primordial images and symbols residing in the collective unconscious—plays a crucial role in understanding human behavior and mental disorders. The figure of Legion can be interpreted as an archetype representing chaotic, destructive forces within the psyche that, when unacknowledged, can lead to psychological disturbances (Jung, 1968).

Transmutation and Healing

In the context of spiritual disorders, the alchemical approach emphasizes the transformation of negative psychic energies into positive, life-affirming forces. This transformation is akin to the exorcism in the biblical narratives, where the expulsion of demons leads to the restoration of mental and spiritual health (Eliade, 1962).

Psychotherapy and Societal Mental Health

Psychotherapy, distinct from psychiatry and psychology, focuses on understanding and treating the underlying spiritual and mental factors contributing to societal mental health issues. Psychotherapists address the spread of mind viruses—negative patterns of thought and behavior that permeate society, much like infectious diseases.

Mind Viruses and Cultural Transmission

The concept of mind viruses, introduced by Richard Brodie in his book "Virus of the Mind: The New Science of the Meme" (Brodie, 1996), refers to ideas or thought patterns that spread like biological viruses, infecting individuals and societies. These mind viruses can manifest as harmful behaviors and attitudes, such as profanity, promiscuity, deceit, and violence, which perpetuate mental disorders and societal dysfunction.

Mind viruses operate by exploiting the host's cognitive processes, embedding themselves deeply within the culture and collective psyche. Unlike traditional mental disorders, which are typically confined to individuals, mind viruses can spread rapidly through populations, facilitated by media, social interactions, and cultural norms (Brodie, 1996; Blackmore, 1999).

These mind viruses lack the identity and destiny attributed to spiritual entities like demons but function similarly to biological viruses by hijacking the host's mental processes. This analogy to biological viruses, which commandeer the host cell's protein synthesis machinery for replication (Koonin & Dolja, 2013), underscores the insidious nature of mind viruses in shaping collective behavior and thought.

The mind viruses are also a byproduct of political discourse and projects by opposing governments to inflict damages to the integrity of the opposing nations and governments, as we explained in the context of psychological warfare (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024).

The Role of the Psychotherapist

The psychotherapist's role is to identify and treat these mind viruses, aiming to restore mental health at both individual and societal levels. This approach requires a deep understanding of the cultural and historical context of mental disorders, as well as the spiritual dimensions of human experience. Psychotherapists work to unravel these negative thought patterns and replace them with positive, constructive ones, much like the process of individuation in Jungian therapy (Jung, 1968).

Psychotherapists also play a crucial role in educating society about the dangers of mind viruses and promoting mental hygiene practices to prevent their spread. This proactive approach is essential in addressing and mitigating the widespread impact of these cultural and mental pathogens (Dawkins, 1976).

Cultural Reflections in Cinema

The Iranian film "The Kingdom of Solomon" serves as a modern cultural reflection of the ancient themes discussed. The movie portrays King Solomon's battle against demons and supernatural forces, echoing the biblical narratives of spiritual warfare and possession. This cinematic representation underscores the enduring relevance of these themes in contemporary society.

The Kingdom of Solomon

In "The Kingdom of Solomon," demons and evil spirits manipulate and control humans, leading to widespread violence and chaos. The film illustrates the belief that only through faith in God can one overcome these malevolent forces, highlighting the spiritual dimensions of mental and social disorders (Bahrani, 2010). This depiction aligns with the Jungian view of integrating the Shadow and the alchemical process of transformation to achieve psychological and spiritual wholeness.

Conclusion

The treatment of social disorders through alchemical, Jungian, and biblical approaches offers a multifaceted understanding of mental health. By integrating these perspectives, we can appreciate the complex interplay between spiritual, psychological, and cultural factors in the manifestation and treatment of mental disorders. The role of the psychotherapist, akin to that of Jesus or Solomon, is crucial in addressing and healing these deep-seated issues, ultimately contributing to the well-being of society.

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Hermeneutics of Luke 18:16-17 in the Course of the Gaza Crisis

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Abstract

Luke 18:16-17 contributes to a great teaching of Jesus with regards to the general acceptance of the children in the so-called kingdom of God. In these narratives from Jesus the terms of religion and ethnicity do not play a role or leave a place for the judgment of the children. In the course of the Gaza crisis so far more than 40,000 (October, 2023-August, 2024) civilians are reported to be killed and among them, around 70 percent are children or women. To understand the hermeneutics of these casualties in one of the worst massacres against children in history, we acknowledge that the kingdom of God in Luke 18:16-17 shall play a role in a Christian or religious approach towards this crisis and separate the truth from falsehood in the background.

Keywords: Gaza, Luke 18:6-17, Children, Bible

Introduction

Luke 18:16-17 contributes to a profound teaching of Jesus regarding the universal acceptance of children in the Kingdom of God. In these verses, Jesus emphasizes the importance of children, symbolizing their innocence, humility, and vulnerability. He instructs His followers to "let the little children come to me, and do not hinder them, for the kingdom of God belongs to such as these" (Luke 18:16, NIV). Jesus' teaching is clear—no distinctions based on religion, ethnicity, or social status should prevent children from being received into God's embrace. In this context, Jesus' message is devoid of judgment and exclusion, demonstrating that God's Kingdom transcends human boundaries and limitations (Green, 1997; Bock, 1994).

This teaching becomes especially relevant in light of the ongoing Gaza crisis, where over 40,000 civilian casualties have been reported, with approximately 70 percent being women and children. Such numbers highlight the devastating impact of this conflict on the most vulnerable members of society—those who, according to Jesus, are to be cherished and protected as recipients of God's Kingdom. The loss of innocent lives in one of the worst massacres against children in modern history raises ethical and theological questions that call for a Christian response grounded in the hermeneutics of Luke 18:16-17.

Through this lens, the casualties of the Gaza conflict can be understood as a tragedy that not only defies moral principles but also contradicts the teachings of Jesus. His call for the acceptance of children and their protection as part of the Kingdom of God demands a response that upholds justice, compassion, and truth. Christians are therefore called to separate the truth from falsehood in this crisis by recognizing the inherent worth and dignity of each child affected by the conflict. The hermeneutics of Luke 18:16-17 challenge believers to advocate for peace and to stand against violence, particularly when it is directed at the innocent and vulnerable (Marshall, 1978; Morris, 1988).

In conclusion, Jesus' words in Luke 18:16-17 provide a foundation for understanding the immense moral weight of civilian casualties, particularly children, in the Gaza conflict. His teaching compels Christians to reject violence and to work towards a world where the innocent, regardless of their ethnicity or religion, are protected and welcomed into the peace of God's Kingdom.

Munter Issac¹ the lead Christina pastor in Gaza describes such devastating war on Gaza as an annihilation and prays for the mercy of The Lord.² He states “ *History books will record that the US Congress hosted a war criminal (Netanyahu) and gave him and outrageous number of standing ovations.*”³

We previously tried to acknowledge the relatedness of the conflict to the Islamic hermeneutics separately using the interconnectedness of the events in the hypothesis of so called Matrix (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b)

Context and Literary Setting

The context of Luke 18 not only highlights Jesus’ teachings on humility, self-righteousness, and the nature of faith but also the acceptance of children in the kingdom of God. Those teaching not only emphasizes of the faith as recorded in most literary articles, but also on the children. Earlier in the chapter, Jesus contrasts the self-righteousness of the Pharisee with the humility of the tax collector (Luke 18:9-14). Following this, Jesus turns His attention to children, symbolizing their purity and innocence as a model for how people should approach God.

At the time, children were considered insignificant in social and religious hierarchies, so for Jesus to affirm their place in God’s Kingdom was radical. It challenged prevailing cultural norms and pointed to a deeper truth about God’s value system. Rather than strength, status, or intellect, God desires a posture of humility and trust—qualities often found in children (Green, 1997).

Key Themes and Theological Implications

1. Childlike Faith and Humility

Jesus’ invitation for the children to come to Him (v. 16) highlights His compassion and acceptance of those deemed lowly in society. The children represent humility, vulnerability, and an openness to receiving love and care from others. Jesus’ admonition that “the

¹ Palestinian Christian Theologian. Evangelical Lutheran Pastor in Bethlehem. Academic Dean of Beth Bible College. Retrieved from X (Former Twitter): <https://x.com/muntherisaac>

² <https://x.com/MuntherIsaac/status/1764538524148048215>

³ <https://x.com/MuntherIsaac/status/1816177713637642718>

Kingdom of God belongs to them” implies that these qualities are essential for anyone who wishes to enter God’s Kingdom.

According to biblical scholars, the idea of "childlike" faith does not imply naivety but a dependence on God’s grace, akin to how children rely on their parents. Stein (1992) notes that Jesus' teaching here advocates a faith that is unpretentious and sincere—marked by a wholehearted trust in God’s provision and guidance.

2. Reception of the Kingdom

Jesus’ statement in verse 17, "If anyone does not receive the kingdom of God like a child, he will never enter it," introduces a strong condition for entrance into the Kingdom of God. To "receive" the Kingdom like a child means to accept it with the same innocence, trust, and lack of pretension that a child would show when receiving a gift. The childlike reception is not passive but active in its trust and surrender to God’s will (Marshall, 1978).

Theologically, this points to the necessity of approaching God with humility and recognizing our own spiritual poverty. Just as a child depends on their parents, so must believers depend fully on God’s grace and mercy for salvation (Bock, 1994).

3. The Kingdom Belongs to Children

Jesus' radical redefinition of worth in God’s Kingdom suggests that God’s rule overturns societal structures and values. While the world often celebrates power, wealth, and prestige, the Kingdom of God is for those who embody simplicity and trust. As Morris (1988) explains, Jesus’ teaching here challenges the adult preoccupation with control, autonomy, and self-sufficiency—characteristics that can hinder one's relationship with God. Children are free beings whose food and necessities are provided or shall be provided by their parents, therefore no greed or tyranny for monetary wealth and occupations are among them. The teachings which emphasize on the children financial learning and their greed are thus considered against the natural freedom of children.

This emphasis on the lowly and humble is a consistent theme in Luke's Gospel. The Magnificat (Luke 1:46-55), for example, celebrates God’s exaltation of the humble and the bringing down of the proud. Jesus’ association with the marginalized, including

children, lepers, and sinners, reiterates the values of God's Kingdom as being in opposition to worldly standards of worth.

Conclusion

Luke 18:16-17 serves as a critical teaching in the Christian faith, illustrating the importance of childlike receptivity to the Kingdom of God. In addition to its reference to faith, the importance and acceptance of children are embodied in the text calling God as the master and king of the children. In the current Gaza crisis where an immense war against children has been unfolded, with any excuses the children are sacrificed against the teachings of Jesus. We already explained that the context of wisdom, religion and science are diverged in the course of immense conflicts like the ongoing crisis in Gaza (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) and religious teachings find their meaning in the course of such events. The true faith shall be found in the pragmatic acceptance of the teachings and not through empty words or repetitions. Through this passage, Jesus conveys that humility, trust, and dependence of children on God as essential qualities for those who wish to enter His Kingdom. The challenge to approach God without pretense or self-righteousness, like a child, reflects the broader theme of humility found throughout Luke's Gospel.

By embracing this childlike faith, believers can experience the fullness of God's Kingdom, which is not based on human merit but on God's grace. This teaching remains a vital reminder for Christians to cultivate humility and reliance on God in their spiritual journey.

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